

JFRA

Journal of Financial Reporting and Analysis

Journal homepage: <http://www.jfra.sp.ng>

The Moderating Effect of Board Independence on CEO Tenure and Firm Performance

VICTORIA AMACHUKWU^a, ONIPE ADABENEGBE YAHAYA^b

^a*Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria*

^b*Faculty of Management Sciences, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria*

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the moderating effect of board independence on the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance. The purpose of this research is to explore whether firms led by female CEOs perform differently than those led by male CEOs, and how the level of board independence influences this dynamic. The research adopts a quantitative methodology, utilizing a panel data set of publicly listed firms from 2014 to 2023 across eleven (11) industries. Regression analysis is employed to assess firm performance, measured by Tobin's Q while controlling for variables such as audit quality, firm size, and leverage. Board independence is quantified by the percentage of independent directors on the board. The findings reveal that all the variables are significant in terms of Tobin's Q, but this effect is significantly moderated by board independence. Specifically, in firms with higher levels of board independence, the positive impact of CEOs tenure on firm performance is amplified. These results suggest that board independence plays a critical role in maximizing the potential benefits of tenure in leadership. The implications of this study extend to both corporate governance practices and tenure diversity initiatives. Firms should not only aim to increase tenure diversity in executive roles but also focus on enhancing board independence to unlock the full potential of diverse leadership. Policymakers and regulators may also consider the findings when framing guidelines for board composition and tenure representation in leadership. Limitations of the study include the use of archival data, which may not fully capture the nuances of board dynamics, and the potential for omitted variable bias due to unobserved firm characteristics. Additionally, the study is geographically limited to publicly listed firms in a single country, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. This research contributes original insights by combining two streams of literature—tenure diversity and corporate governance—offering a nuanced understanding of how board independence can influence the CEO tenure–firm performance relationship.

JEL Classification: C23, C58, C87, M21, M24, M48

Keywords: Audit quality, board independence, CEO tenure, firm performance, firm size, leverage.

Article history:

Received: 10 January 2024

Accepted: 27 Sept 2024

* Corresponding author: Email: victoria.amachukwu@unn.edu.ng

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.26431/jfra.v9i27>

© Journal of Financial Reporting and Analysis. ISSN 2643-111X.

INTRODUCTION

Scholars have examined several different ways and means to improve firm performance (Abdulwahab et al., 2023; Abubakar et al., 2023; Ahmed & Yahaya, 2024; Aliyu et al., 2021; Apochi et al., 2022a; Apochi et al., 2022b; Haruna & Yahaya, 2024; Ibrahim & Yahaya, 2023; Kabir et al., 2023; Lamido et al., 2023; Lawal & Yahaya, 2024; Mironenkova & Yahaya, 2024; Opeyemi et al., 2020; Suleiman et al., 2022; Suleiman et al., 2024; Tighil et al., 2024; Yahaya, 2014, 2017, 2018, 2022; Yahaya et al., 2014; Yahaya & Lamidi, 2015; Yahaya & Lamido, 2022; Yahaya & Onyabe, 2020; Yahaya & Yusuf, 2020; Yahaya et al., 2015a; Yahaya et al., 2015b; Yahaya et al., 2019; Yahaya & Andow, 2015; Yahaya & Alexandra, 2015; Yusuf & Yahaya, 2023). Low firm performance has been a persistent concern among a wide range of stakeholders because it threatens the stability, growth, and sustainability of businesses, economies, and entire industries. Each group of stakeholders—scholars, regulators, corporate owners, managers, creditors, employees, and tax agencies—has a vested interest in firm performance, as it directly impacts their financial health, strategic objectives, and long-term viability.

Scholars and researchers are deeply concerned with low firm performance because it represents a critical area of study for understanding business sustainability, efficiency, and corporate governance. Firms that consistently underperform provide valuable case studies on the limitations of existing management theories, corporate governance practices, and economic models. Scholars explore the root causes of poor performance, whether due to inefficient resource allocation, weak leadership, market misalignment, or external economic shocks. Moreover, low firm performance helps scholars develop new models of firm behaviour, strategic management, and competitive advantage. This area also intersects with studies on organizational resilience and crisis management, as scholars investigate how firms can recover from or prevent prolonged downturns.

Regulators, including government agencies and financial market authorities, are concerned with low firm performance due to its potential ripple effects on broader economic stability and investor protection. Underperforming firms are more likely to engage in practices that skirt regulatory frameworks to maintain short-term profitability, such as manipulating financial statements, underreporting liabilities, or reducing compliance with industry standards. These behaviours can undermine market transparency and lead to financial crises if widespread. Additionally, regulators aim to safeguard the interests of minority shareholders and the general public by ensuring that firms operate in a manner that promotes long-term stability rather than short-term gains. Poorly performing firms are also more likely to default on loans and contracts, which poses risks to the financial system.

Corporate owners, including shareholders and private equity investors, are directly impacted by low firm performance as it erodes shareholder value and diminishes returns on investment. For public companies, this concern is heightened by market perceptions, where prolonged poor performance can lead to declining stock prices and loss of investor confidence. For private firms, low performance can hinder the ability to raise capital, innovate, or expand operations. Moreover, owners may become concerned about managerial competence, strategic direction, and misalignment between management incentives and shareholder interests. In the case of family-owned businesses, low performance could endanger the firm's legacy, continuity, and multigenerational wealth transfer.

Managers, especially CEOs and senior executives, are at the forefront of addressing firm performance. Low performance often reflects poorly on their leadership and strategic decision-making capabilities, making them accountable to owners and boards of directors. Managers face pressure to deliver results, and prolonged periods of underperformance can lead to leadership turnover, restructuring, or even bankruptcy in extreme cases. Moreover, low firm performance limits managerial ability to implement long-term growth strategies, innovate, or respond to competitive pressures. Managers may also face conflicts of interest, as short-term fixes like cost-cutting or workforce downsizing might improve profitability but compromise long-term sustainability. Therefore, maintaining performance becomes critical to job security, reputation, and career progression.

Creditors—such as banks, bondholders, and other lending institutions—view low firm performance as a heightened credit risk. Underperforming firms may struggle to meet debt obligations, increasing the likelihood of defaults or late payments. For banks, this creates risks in their loan portfolios, which may require them to

increase reserves for bad loans, thereby affecting their own profitability and stability. Bondholders face the possibility of losing their capital or receiving lower-than-expected returns. Moreover, when firms underperform, their credit ratings may be downgraded, increasing borrowing costs and further exacerbating liquidity challenges. Consequently, creditors may tighten credit terms, demand higher collateral, or even refuse to extend additional credit, leading to a vicious cycle that further worsens firm performance.

Employees are deeply affected by low firm performance, which often leads to job insecurity, layoffs, wage freezes, or reduced benefits. A firm's financial health directly impacts its ability to maintain and grow its workforce. During times of poor performance, firms may resort to downsizing or restructuring, which can demoralize the workforce and diminish organizational culture. Employees may also experience reduced career development opportunities as firms cut costs by limiting training, promotions, and skill development initiatives. Additionally, low firm performance reduces the firm's ability to attract and retain top talent, as high performers may seek more stable and financially sound employers. This can create a cycle of declining morale, productivity, and overall firm capacity, exacerbating the firm's challenges.

Government tax agencies are concerned with low firm performance because it can lead to reduced tax revenues. Poorly performing firms may generate lower profits, leading to a smaller tax base from which income taxes can be drawn. Furthermore, struggling firms may seek tax relief, subsidies, or other forms of government assistance, placing additional burdens on public finances. In extreme cases, tax agencies may face difficulties collecting unpaid taxes from bankrupt firms, leading to revenue losses. Poor firm performance may also reduce employment levels, impacting payroll tax contributions and social security funding. From a macroeconomic perspective, widespread low performance can lead to economic stagnation, further constraining tax revenue collection at both the local and national levels.

Customers: Low firm performance can lead to reduced product quality, innovation, and customer service as firms struggle to maintain competitiveness. This can result in decreased customer satisfaction and loyalty. Suppliers: Underperforming firms may face liquidity issues, leading to delays in payments to suppliers or renegotiation of contracts under less favourable terms. Communities: Firms that are major employers or economic anchors in their communities may reduce their local investments, sponsorships, or contributions to social welfare programs during times of poor performance, thereby negatively impacting the broader community. In conclusion, low firm performance is not an isolated concern but a multi-dimensional issue that affects a broad spectrum of stakeholders. From financial instability to loss of trust, low firm performance has cascading effects on the economic ecosystem, making it a pressing issue for corporate governance and strategic management. Effective performance management is thus essential not only for firm survival but also for the protection of stakeholder interests across the board. These concerns highlight the need for robust corporate governance structures, sound leadership, and innovative strategies to help firms navigate periods of underperformance and emerge stronger.

Improving firm performance is a multifaceted endeavour that requires strategic action across various dimensions of an organization. Whether the firm is experiencing operational inefficiencies, leadership challenges, market pressures, or financial constraints, improving performance typically involves targeted interventions to enhance competitiveness, productivity, innovation, and stakeholder engagement. Below are several robust ways in which firm performance can be improved: Effective leadership is crucial for setting the strategic vision, driving organizational change, and ensuring alignment with corporate goals. Leaders who demonstrate clarity, decisiveness, and adaptability can inspire teams to improve performance through innovation and collaboration. Developing a leadership pipeline that focuses on transformational leadership, emotional intelligence, and decision-making can result in better organizational performance. Board Oversight: The quality of corporate governance plays a significant role in firm performance. An independent, diverse, and skilled board of directors can provide strategic oversight and challenge the status quo, ensuring that executive decisions are made in the firm's long-term interest. Strengthening the role of independent directors in monitoring management performance and risk management can also enhance decision-making quality. Alignment of CEO Compensation with Performance: Linking executive compensation to firm performance metrics such as return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), or earnings per share (EPS) ensures that CEOs are motivated to drive sustainable value creation rather than pursue short-term gains.

Optimizing Operational Efficiency - Process Improvement: Firms can implement continuous process improvement techniques like Lean, Six Sigma, or Total Quality Management (TQM) to reduce inefficiencies, eliminate waste, and enhance product or service quality. Streamlining processes can result in lower costs, faster production times, and improved customer satisfaction. Automation and Technology Integration: Leveraging

technology to automate routine tasks can significantly enhance operational efficiency. Implementing Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning tools in operations, finance, and customer service can increase accuracy, reduce operational costs, and free up resources for more strategic activities. Cloud computing and data analytics can also provide real-time insights, allowing firms to make more informed, data-driven decisions. Supply Chain Optimization: Improving supply chain management by optimizing inventory levels, improving supplier relationships, and using advanced logistics can lead to cost reductions and improved delivery times. Firms should adopt just-in-time (JIT) inventory management to reduce excess inventory and minimize holding costs, while also ensuring that they have contingency plans for supply chain disruptions.

Strategic Innovation and R&D - Product and Service Innovation: To improve long-term performance, firms must focus on innovation as a competitive differentiator. By investing in research and development (R&D), firms can develop new products, services, or business models that meet emerging customer needs or disrupt existing markets. A commitment to innovation often leads to higher market share and profitability, as well as positioning the firm as an industry leader. Open Innovation: Collaborating with external partners—such as universities, research institutions, and other firms—can help firms access new technologies, ideas, and markets. This approach can drive faster innovation cycles and reduce the risk of failure compared to in-house R&D alone. Digital Transformation: Embracing digital transformation is essential for firms aiming to stay relevant in an increasingly digital world. This involves integrating digital technologies into all areas of the business to fundamentally change how it operates and delivers value to customers. Digital transformation can enhance customer experience, streamline operations, and generate new revenue streams.

Focusing on Customer-Centric Strategies - Customer Relationship Management (CRM): Firms that place a high priority on understanding and meeting customer needs often outperform those that do not. Implementing CRM systems allows firms to track customer preferences, purchase behaviours, and feedback, which can inform product development and marketing strategies. Personalizing customer experiences, offering exceptional after-sales service, and maintaining strong communication channels are vital for customer retention and satisfaction. Value Proposition Enhancement: By continuously refining and enhancing their value propositions, firms can differentiate themselves from competitors. This could involve improving product features, offering better pricing, or bundling services to deliver more value. Firms that regularly adapt their value propositions to changing market conditions and customer preferences tend to perform better over time. Loyalty Programs: Implementing customer loyalty programs that reward repeat purchases or long-term relationships can increase customer lifetime value and reduce churn. These programs also encourage brand advocacy and referrals, contributing to long-term revenue growth.

Human Capital Development - Employee Engagement and Satisfaction: A motivated, engaged workforce directly correlates with better firm performance. Firms should invest in creating a positive work environment where employees feel valued and empowered. This can be achieved through fair compensation, career development opportunities, recognition programs, and promoting work-life balance. Engaged employees are more productive, innovative, and committed to achieving company goals. Training and Development: Continuous learning and professional development are essential for keeping employees skilled and adaptive to changing industry demands. Firms that offer regular training, reskilling, and upskilling opportunities enable their workforce to stay competitive and innovate. This is particularly important in industries undergoing rapid technological advancements. Leadership Development: Developing internal leadership talent ensures that the firm has capable leaders who can step into critical roles as the business grows or as current leaders transition. A well-structured leadership development program ensures continuity and enhances overall firm performance by maintaining strong strategic direction.

Financial Management and Capital Allocation - Cost Management and Budgeting: Prudent financial management is crucial for improving firm performance. Firms need to closely monitor costs, implement cost-cutting measures where necessary, and ensure efficient use of capital. This includes conducting regular financial audits, renegotiating supplier contracts, and scrutinizing operational expenses to identify areas where savings can be made without compromising quality or service delivery. Capital Structure Optimization: Maintaining an optimal capital structure—balancing between debt and equity—ensures that firms can meet their financial

obligations while also maximizing shareholder value. Firms with too much debt may face high interest payments that erode profits, while firms with too little debt may miss out on growth opportunities. Striking the right balance between equity financing, retained earnings, and debt financing can improve financial stability and overall firm performance. Cash Flow Management: Effective cash flow management ensures that the firm has adequate liquidity to meet short-term liabilities and fund operational needs. Firms should optimize their working capital cycles, such as accounts receivable, inventory, and accounts payable, to maintain a healthy cash flow.

Strategic Alliances and Partnerships - Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A): Firms can improve performance by pursuing mergers, acquisitions, or strategic alliances that allow them to access new markets, technologies, or capabilities. M&A activity can create synergies by combining resources, improving operational efficiencies, and reducing redundancies, thereby boosting overall firm performance. However, M&A deals need to be carefully planned and executed to avoid integration challenges or cultural misalignments. Joint Ventures and Strategic Partnerships: Collaborating with other firms to achieve shared objectives—whether for R&D, market entry, or cost-sharing—can improve performance. Joint ventures can allow firms to access new resources or markets while spreading risks and costs. Strategic alliances can also help firms respond more effectively to competitive threats or economic challenges.

Adapting to Market Changes and Competitive Dynamics - Agility and Flexibility: Firms that are agile and able to quickly adapt to changes in market conditions, consumer preferences, or technological advancements tend to outperform less flexible competitors. Emphasizing a culture of agility—where teams can pivot quickly in response to opportunities or challenges—can ensure that the firm remains competitive in dynamic markets.

Competitive Benchmarking: Regularly comparing firm performance to industry benchmarks and best practices can help firms identify gaps and opportunities for improvement. By learning from top-performing competitors and adapting best practices, firms can close performance gaps and enhance their competitive positioning.

Sustainability and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) - Sustainability Initiatives: Firms that adopt sustainable business practices—such as reducing carbon footprints, minimizing waste, and implementing eco-friendly processes—often improve their long-term performance. Sustainability is increasingly valued by consumers, investors, and regulators, and firms that embrace it can improve brand loyalty, reduce costs, and gain access to new markets. CSR Engagement: Engaging in corporate social responsibility can enhance a firm's reputation, foster positive relationships with stakeholders, and improve employee satisfaction. CSR activities that align with the firm's core values and business strategy can create a positive public image, leading to stronger customer loyalty and better financial performance over time. In conclusion, improving firm performance requires a holistic approach that addresses leadership, operational efficiency, innovation, customer-centric strategies, human capital, financial management, strategic partnerships, and adaptability to market dynamics. Firms that excel in these areas are better positioned to achieve sustainable growth, profitability, and long-term competitiveness. Regular evaluation and refinement of these strategies are essential for continuous improvement and resilience in an ever-changing business environment.

Although, while there are several strategies to improve firm performance as discussed in the foregoing paragraph, the focus of this paper is to examine the moderating effect of board independence on CEO tenure and firm performance in Nigeria. The moderating effect of board independence on the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance is a critical area of study in corporate governance, leadership diversity, and firm outcomes. Understanding how board independence can influence this relationship requires an exploration of tenure dynamics in executive leadership, the role of independent boards in governance, and the broader mechanisms through which these factors interact to affect firm performance. Below is a robust and elaborate examination of this phenomenon.

CEO Tenure and Firm Performance: The Direct Relationship. Over the past decades, research has examined whether CEO tenure affects firm performance, driven by the increasing presence of female executives in corporate leadership roles. This has sparked interest due to the potential differences in leadership styles, risk aversion, decision-making processes, and stakeholder management approaches between male and female CEOs. The Key Findings in the CEO Tenure-Firm Performance Relationship: Leadership Style Differences: Studies have found that female CEOs often adopt more collaborative and inclusive leadership styles compared to their male counterparts, who may lean towards more hierarchical or autocratic approaches. Women in leadership tend to emphasize team-building, long-term sustainability, and stakeholder engagement, which may positively affect firm performance by fostering innovation and employee morale. Risk Aversion: Some research suggests that female CEOs tend to be more risk-averse than male CEOs. This may result in more conservative financial strategies, which can lead to stable performance, particularly during times of economic uncertainty or market

volatility. However, it could also limit the firm's ability to capitalize on high-risk, high-reward opportunities. Social Impact and CSR: Female CEOs may be more likely to prioritize corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives and other sustainability practices. Firms led by women have been shown to invest more in environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors, which can enhance reputation and long-term value creation, contributing to positive firm outcomes. Market Reactions and Biases: Market reactions to female leadership are complex and sometimes biased. Some studies suggest that investors and stakeholders may initially undervalue female-led firms due to unconscious biases or stereotypes, which can negatively affect stock performance in the short term, even if operational performance remains strong.

Board Independence: Definition and Importance: Board independence refers to the presence of independent, non-executive directors on a company's board who do not have a material relationship with the company other than their directorship. Independent directors are expected to provide objective oversight, free from internal pressures or conflicts of interest, and play a crucial role in ensuring that management acts in the best interests of shareholders. The Functions and Benefits of Board Independence: Oversight and Monitoring: Independent boards are more likely to hold the CEO and management accountable for their decisions, ensuring that they align with shareholder interests. This is especially important when firm leadership, including the CEO, might be tempted to pursue personal goals (such as empire-building) over maximizing shareholder value. Decision-Making Quality: Independent directors can provide diverse perspectives and challenge management's assumptions, leading to more robust decision-making. This can prevent "groupthink" and improve the quality of strategic choices. Risk Management: Independent boards are more likely to take a balanced approach to risk, ensuring that CEOs do not engage in excessively risky strategies that could jeopardize firm stability. Alignment with Shareholders: Independent directors serve as a bridge between the firm's management and its shareholders, ensuring that corporate strategies are designed to enhance long-term shareholder value rather than serve short-term executive interests.

The Moderating Effect of Board Independence on CEO Tenure and Firm Performance: The relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance is not always straightforward and may be contingent on several factors, including board independence. Board independence can moderate this relationship by amplifying or mitigating the effects of CEO tenure on firm performance. Amplifying the Positive Impact of Female CEOs: Research shows that female CEOs often bring diverse perspectives and emphasize long-term goals, ethical leadership, and stakeholder engagement. In firms where there is a high level of board independence, these attributes can be better leveraged because independent boards are likely to recognize and support these strengths. In contrast to non-independent boards, which may resist or undermine a female CEO's initiatives due to entrenched biases or traditional practices, independent boards are more likely to objectively assess the benefits of a female CEO's leadership style and strategies. Support for Strategic Innovation: Independent boards, due to their objective stance, are more likely to encourage and support strategic initiatives brought forward by female CEOs, such as investments in sustainability or corporate social responsibility (CSR) efforts. These initiatives, often associated with long-term value creation, may not be immediately embraced by less independent boards that favor short-term profit maximization. Diverse Decision-Making: When a female CEO works with an independent board, the combined leadership diversity (CEO tenure diversity + board independence) fosters an environment where diverse perspectives thrive, leading to more balanced, inclusive, and well-rounded decisions. This has been linked to better financial outcomes, as firms with diverse decision-making processes tend to outperform those with more homogeneous leadership.

Mitigating Tenure Biases in Leadership Perception: In many firms, female CEOs face skepticism or bias from within the boardroom, which can detract from their ability to lead effectively. Board independence can moderate the CEO tenure–firm performance relationship by reducing the impact of such biases. Independent directors are less likely to be influenced by tenure stereotypes, as their primary focus is on firm performance and value creation. As a result, independent boards can provide fairer assessments of female CEOs' capabilities and strategies, ensuring that tenure biases do not hinder firm performance. Objective Performance Evaluation: Independent boards are more likely to evaluate CEO performance based on tangible metrics (e.g., financial results, market share growth) rather than subjective perceptions or tenure biases. This helps ensure that female CEOs receive support and resources commensurate with their performance, fostering a stronger alignment

between CEO leadership and firm outcomes. **Reduced Tokenism:** In firms with low board independence, female CEOs may be treated as "tokens" and have their authority undermined by boards that do not fully embrace tenure diversity. Independent boards are more likely to provide female CEOs with the autonomy and support necessary to implement their vision, thus reducing the likelihood of tokenism and its negative effects on performance.

Balancing Risk-Taking Behaviour: Female CEOs tend to be more risk-averse compared to male CEOs, a factor that can influence firm performance, especially in volatile markets. Independent boards are well-positioned to moderate the potential extremes of risk aversion or risk-taking. **For example: Encouraging Risk-Taking:** If the board sees that a female CEO's risk aversion is limiting the firm's ability to pursue growth opportunities, independent directors can encourage a more balanced approach, advocating for calculated risks that drive innovation and expansion. **Constraining Excessive Risk:** Conversely, in the case of male CEOs who may lean towards riskier strategies, independent boards can play a critical role in curbing excessive risk-taking behaviors that could endanger firm performance.

Empirical Evidence: CEO Tenure, Board Independence, and Firm Performance: Several empirical studies suggest that board independence strengthens the positive effects of female CEOs on firm performance. **For example:** A study by Adams and Ferreira (2009) found that firms with more tenure-diverse boards, which include independent directors, perform better under female leadership. The diversity brought by both the female CEO and the independent board leads to more rigorous oversight, better decision-making, and improved financial outcomes. Research by Liu, Wei, and Xie (2014) found that board independence plays a moderating role in enhancing the positive relationship between female leadership and corporate social responsibility (CSR), which in turn positively impacts firm performance. Studies also indicate that female CEOs tend to be more effective in governance structures that provide them with strong oversight and autonomy, and independent boards are more likely to offer that balance compared to boards dominated by insiders.

Challenges and Limitations: While the moderating effect of board independence can positively influence the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance, certain challenges persist: **Cultural Resistance:** In some regions or industries, even independent boards may be influenced by cultural norms or biases that undervalue female leadership. This limits the extent to which board independence can mitigate tenure biases. **Measurement of Independence:** Not all "independent" boards are truly independent. Some nominally independent directors may still have close ties to the firm or management, which could dilute their effectiveness in moderating the CEO tenure–firm performance relationship. **Industry-Specific Factors:** The impact of CEO tenure and board independence may vary across industries. For example, industries with high levels of competition or innovation may benefit more from diverse leadership and independent oversight than more traditional, regulated industries. In conclusion, the moderating effect of board independence on the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance is substantial. Independent boards can enhance the positive contributions of female CEOs by providing unbiased oversight, encouraging strategic innovation, and fostering balanced decision-making. By reducing the effects of tenure biases and promoting objective evaluation, independent boards ensure that the firm fully benefits from diverse leadership. However, the effectiveness of this moderation depends on the true independence of the board and the cultural or industry-specific context in which the firm operates. Ultimately, the combination of tenure diversity in leadership and strong board governance offers a powerful means of improving firm performance and driving long-term success. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section two reviews the related literature. Section three explains the methodological approach. Section four presents the results. Section five concludes and recommends.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Firm Performance (FP)

Firm performance refers to how well a company or organization achieves its financial, operational, and strategic goals over a specific period. It is a critical measure of a company's success, reflecting its efficiency, profitability, competitiveness, and overall health. Firm performance is multifaceted, covering various dimensions such as profitability, revenue growth, market share, productivity, and shareholder value. These metrics help stakeholders—ranging from investors and managers to employees and regulators—assess the company's progress, stability, and future prospects. The Key Dimensions of Firm Performance include **Profitability:** This includes measures such as net income, return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), and earnings before interest and taxes (EBIT). Profitability shows how effectively a firm is generating earnings relative to its costs.

Revenue Growth: Growing revenues indicate that a company is expanding its market presence or improving sales performance. Metrics such as total revenue, sales growth rate, and customer acquisition can offer insights into this aspect. **Liquidity and Solvency:** These metrics show a firm's ability to meet short-term obligations (liquidity) and long-term debts (solvency). Ratios such as the current ratio, quick ratio, and debt-to-equity ratio are common measures of financial stability. **Market Value and Shareholder Returns:** The value of a firm as reflected in stock prices, dividends, and overall returns to shareholders. Metrics like total shareholder return (TSR) and price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio are used.

Operational Performance: Efficiency: Measures such as asset turnover, inventory turnover, and operational costs help evaluate how efficiently a firm uses its resources to generate output. **Productivity:** This refers to how effectively a firm converts inputs (labour, capital, materials) into outputs (goods or services). Labor productivity and total factor productivity (TFP) are common measures. **Quality of Products/Services:** High-quality outputs lead to greater customer satisfaction, loyalty, and market competitiveness, all of which are tied to better performance in the long run.

Market Performance: Market Share: A company's share in the market relative to competitors is a critical measure of its performance, especially in highly competitive industries. **Customer Retention and Acquisition:** The ability to maintain and grow a customer base directly impacts revenue and profitability. **Strategic Performance: Innovation and Growth Initiatives:** Firms that successfully innovate and diversify their products or services tend to perform better. This includes research and development (R&D) investment, patent filings, and product launches. **Strategic Alignment:** Firms that align their operations with their long-term strategic goals often perform better. Strategic initiatives such as market expansion, mergers and acquisitions, or cost leadership are part of this. **Social and Environmental Performance: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR):** Firms that invest in socially responsible activities and sustainable practices often see enhanced reputation and stakeholder trust, which can translate into long-term financial performance. **Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Factors:** Increasingly, firms are evaluated based on their ESG performance, as this reflects their long-term sustainability and ethical operations.

Factors Affecting Firm Performance: Several factors influence firm performance, and they can be both internal and external: **Leadership and Corporate Governance:** Effective leadership and strong governance structures can drive better decision-making and operational oversight, leading to superior firm performance. Conversely, poor leadership and weak governance can result in strategic missteps and financial losses. **Competitive Advantage:** Firms that maintain a competitive edge through innovation, cost leadership, or product differentiation often perform better. Competitive advantage allows firms to attract customers, expand market share, and sustain profitability. **Market Conditions:** External economic factors such as inflation, interest rates, consumer demand, and industry trends play a critical role in influencing firm performance. For instance, firms in growth industries may experience better performance compared to those in declining sectors. **Human Capital:** A skilled and engaged workforce enhances productivity, innovation, and customer satisfaction, directly contributing to firm performance. Conversely, high turnover rates or a lack of talent can negatively impact outcomes. **Technology and Innovation:** Firms that adopt cutting-edge technologies and invest in R&D often improve their performance by enhancing efficiency, creating new products, and staying ahead of competitors. **Operational Efficiency:** Streamlining operations, reducing costs, and maximizing output from available resources contribute to better financial performance and competitive positioning. **Risk Management:** Firms with robust risk management practices can navigate market uncertainties, regulatory changes, and other external threats better, leading to more stable performance.

The Importance of Measuring Firm Performance: Measuring firm performance is essential for multiple reasons:- **Investor Confidence:** Investors and shareholders rely on performance metrics to make informed decisions about buying, holding, or selling shares. A firm's stock price and dividend history are often tied to its financial and operational performance. **Strategic Decision-Making:** Performance assessments guide management in setting future strategies, whether in areas of cost-cutting, innovation, or expansion. **Employee Motivation and Retention:** Companies that perform well tend to provide better job security, growth opportunities, and incentives to employees, fostering higher motivation and retention. **Regulatory Compliance:** Many industries require firms to report performance data to ensure compliance with laws and regulations, ensuring transparency and

accountability. In conclusion, firm performance is a comprehensive indicator of a company's success and longevity. Improving performance requires focusing on leadership, operational efficiency, financial management, market positioning, and innovation. Regularly assessing performance through financial and non-financial metrics enables firms to adapt to changing market conditions, enhance their competitive edge, and achieve long-term sustainable growth. In this paper, FP is seen as Tobin's Q, though, a market-based measure of FP. Thus, Tobin's Q is a financial ratio that compares the market value of a company's assets to their replacement cost. It is named after economist James Tobin, who proposed that firms should be valued based on the ratio of the market value of their assets to the cost of replacing them. Tobin's Q is primarily used to assess whether a firm is overvalued or undervalued relative to the cost of replicating its assets. Interpretation of Tobin's Q: Tobin's Q = 1: The market value of a firm is equal to the replacement cost of its assets. This suggests that the firm is fairly valued—investors are valuing the firm in line with the cost of replacing its assets. Tobin's Q > 1: The market value exceeds the replacement cost of the firm's assets. This may indicate that the firm is overvalued, as investors are willing to pay more for the firm's assets than what it would cost to replace them. In theory, this could signal a good time to build new firms, as they would be cheaper to construct than to buy in the market. Tobin's Q < 1: The market value is less than the replacement cost of the firm's assets. This suggests the firm is undervalued, meaning that the stock price does not fully reflect the value of its underlying assets. In such cases, the firm may be seen as a takeover target or as an attractive investment.

Factors Affecting Tobin's Q: Market Sentiment: A company's stock price is influenced by investor sentiment, which can affect the market value of its assets. Bullish markets may drive up Tobin's Q even if the underlying asset replacement costs remain constant. Innovation and Intangible Assets: Companies with high levels of intellectual property, innovation, or brand value (intangible assets) often have Tobin's Q values greater than 1 because these assets are not easily replicable, and the market tends to price these firms at a premium. Macroeconomic Conditions: Economic factors such as inflation, interest rates, and capital costs can influence both the market value of firms and the replacement cost of assets. Changes in the cost of capital can shift Tobin's Q over time. Growth Prospects: Companies with strong growth prospects often have a Tobin's Q ratio greater than 1 because the market values them based on future earnings potential, which increases the market value above the current replacement cost of assets.

The Applications of Tobin's Q: Investment Decisions: Investors use Tobin's Q to identify whether firms are overvalued or undervalued. Firms with a Tobin's Q below 1 might represent investment opportunities as they are undervalued relative to their asset base. Corporate Strategy: Companies might analyze their Tobin's Q to make decisions about mergers, acquisitions, or capital investments. A low Q could signal that buying other firms or assets is more cost-effective than building new capacity. Macroeconomic Analysis: Tobin's Q can also be used at the aggregate level to assess market valuations relative to the overall economy. For instance, a high average Tobin's Q across the market could signal an overvaluation of firms, potentially indicating a bubble.

However, the Limitations of Tobin's Q: Difficulties in Measuring Replacement Costs: Estimating the replacement cost of a firm's assets is challenging, especially for firms with significant intangible assets (like patents, trademarks, or brand value). These costs may not be accurately reflected in traditional balance sheet items. Influence of Market Fluctuations: The market value of assets can fluctuate significantly over short periods due to changes in stock prices, even if the underlying replacement cost of the firm's assets remains the same. Inapplicability to Service-Oriented Firms: Tobin's Q is more relevant to firms with significant physical assets, such as manufacturing companies. It is less useful for service-based or technology-driven companies, where intangible assets dominate. In conclusion: Tobin's Q is a valuable tool for assessing a firm's market value in relation to the cost of its assets, providing insights into overvaluation or undervaluation. It offers guidance for investors and managers on whether the firm is priced appropriately in the market. However, given the challenges in estimating replacement costs and the influence of intangible assets, it is most useful when combined with other valuation metrics.

The tenure of a CEO can significantly influence firm performance, corporate culture, and decision-making. In recent years, increasing attention has been paid to the role of CEO tenure in shaping corporate outcomes, particularly as more women ascend to leadership positions in major corporations. The impact of CEO tenure on firm performance and governance can vary based on several factors, including the industry, firm size, and the broader cultural or regulatory environment. Key Areas of Discussion Around CEO Tenure: Tenure Diversity in Leadership. Representation: Historically, corporate leadership has been male-dominated, with women often underrepresented in executive roles. As of recent years, although there has been progress, women still occupy a minority of CEO positions, particularly in large, publicly traded companies. Policy and Legislation: In some

regions, policies aimed at increasing tenure diversity on corporate boards and in executive positions (such as quotas or reporting requirements) have been implemented, driving an increase in female leadership.

Impact on Firm Performance: Mixed Empirical Findings: The relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance has produced mixed results in academic studies: Some studies suggest that female CEOs tend to foster better risk management, long-term strategic planning, and a focus on sustainable growth, which can lead to improved firm performance, particularly in volatile or innovation-driven industries. Other studies argue that the effect of CEO tenure on performance is neutral, as leadership effectiveness is more closely tied to the individual's management style, experience, and strategic vision rather than their tenure. **Risk Tolerance:** Research suggests that women leaders may exhibit a more conservative or cautious approach to risk compared to male leaders, which can affect decision-making in areas such as investment, mergers and acquisitions, or financial leverage. This could lead to lower risk-taking in firms with female CEOs, which might stabilize performance in uncertain markets but potentially limit aggressive growth strategies. **Investor Reactions:** Female CEOs sometimes face increased scrutiny from investors, who may exhibit biases based on preconceived notions about tenure and leadership. These biases can affect stock prices, especially in the short term, though many studies indicate no long-term difference in financial performance once other factors are controlled.

Corporate Governance and Culture - Diversity in Decision-Making: Female CEOs are often associated with promoting greater diversity and inclusion within firms, both in terms of tenure and other dimensions (race, background, etc.). This can lead to a more collaborative leadership style, fostering a work environment that values different perspectives. **Board Dynamics:** Companies with female CEOs often have more diverse boards, which has been linked to more robust governance practices. A diverse board tends to better oversee management and mitigate risks by providing varied perspectives. **Leadership Style Differences: Collaborative vs. Authoritative:** Research often highlights tenure-related differences in leadership styles. Female CEOs are more likely to engage in collaborative, team-oriented leadership, focusing on communication and consensus-building. Male CEOs, on the other hand, are often described as more authoritative or top-down in decision-making. While these are general trends and do not apply universally, the collaborative style has been shown to be effective in certain corporate environments. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Female leaders are often associated with a stronger focus on corporate social responsibility (CSR), ethical leadership, and stakeholder engagement. Firms led by women may prioritize long-term sustainability and community engagement, which can enhance corporate reputation and contribute to firm performance indirectly.

Barriers and Challenges for CEOs: Glass Ceiling: Many women face significant barriers to reaching top executive positions, including the so-called glass ceiling, a metaphorical barrier that prevents women from advancing beyond certain managerial levels due to tenure biases and organizational structures. **Tenure Bias and Stereotypes:** Female CEOs often encounter tenure biases, such as assumptions about their leadership abilities, emotional intelligence, and capacity to manage large organizations. These biases can lead to challenges in garnering investor confidence or stakeholder support. **Work-Life Balance:** Women in leadership positions often face societal expectations regarding family responsibilities, which can affect perceptions of their availability or commitment. Despite the changing nature of work, these stereotypes persist and can affect career progression for women in executive roles. **Performance in Crisis Situations:** Some studies have found that female CEOs tend to be appointed more often during times of crisis, a phenomenon called the "glass cliff." This term refers to the tendency of women to be promoted to leadership roles in struggling companies, where the likelihood of failure is higher. Despite these challenging circumstances, many female leaders have demonstrated the ability to stabilize firms and implement recovery strategies, often with a focus on restructuring and innovation. During the COVID-19 pandemic, for example, several female-led companies were recognized for their crisis management, with female CEOs often emphasizing the well-being of employees, community support, and adaptability.

Moderating Factors: Board Independence: The relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance can be moderated by board independence, which refers to the presence of independent (non-executive) directors on the company's board. Independent directors are often tasked with providing oversight and limiting the potential for CEO overreach. Studies suggest that a strong, independent board can complement the leadership of female CEOs by offering strategic guidance and support while mitigating any tenure-related biases that may affect

decision-making. In firms with high board independence, the tenure of the CEO may play less of a role in firm performance, as the board ensures that the focus remains on objective performance metrics and long-term goals. In conclusion, CEO tenure is an important factor that influences corporate performance, leadership style, and governance structures. While female CEOs often face unique challenges such as tenure bias and increased scrutiny, they bring diverse perspectives and leadership styles that can positively affect firm outcomes, particularly in areas such as corporate governance, risk management, and stakeholder engagement. The impact of CEO tenure on firm performance is context-dependent and is often shaped by factors like industry dynamics, board independence, and company culture.

Board independence refers to the presence of non-executive, independent directors on a company's board who are not involved in the day-to-day operations of the firm. Independent directors are those who do not have any significant financial, familial, or professional ties to the company, its executives, or major shareholders. Their primary role is to provide oversight, ensuring that the company is run in the best interests of shareholders and other stakeholders, without undue influence from company insiders, especially the CEO or other top executives. Importance of Board Independence: Oversight and Accountability: Independent directors act as a check on management, particularly the CEO, ensuring that strategic decisions align with the best interests of the shareholders rather than the personal interests of executives. This helps mitigate potential conflicts of interest and reduces the risk of self-serving behaviour by management. Improved Corporate Governance: Board independence is often seen as a hallmark of good corporate governance. Independent directors help ensure transparency and objectivity in the decision-making process, including in areas such as executive compensation, risk management, and major strategic decisions like mergers and acquisitions. Enhancing Shareholder Confidence: Investors often prefer companies with independent boards because it signals that the company is committed to protecting shareholder interests. Firms with more independent boards tend to perform better in governance ratings, which can enhance market confidence and stock performance. Mitigation of CEO Power: Without independent directors, the CEO or other top executives may exert too much influence on board decisions, potentially leading to poor oversight and risky decision-making. Independent directors help ensure that the CEO is held accountable for performance and is not overstepping boundaries.

Key Roles of Independent Directors: Strategic Guidance: Independent board members often bring diverse experiences and expertise, contributing to the formulation of the company's strategy. They can offer objective perspectives on long-term goals, expansion plans, risk management, and innovation. Risk Management: Independent directors play a crucial role in assessing and managing risks. They are involved in overseeing financial risks, regulatory compliance, and ensuring that the firm has sound policies in place to prevent potential legal or ethical issues. Monitoring Executive Performance: Independent directors are often involved in the evaluation and, if necessary, the removal of the CEO. They ensure that executive compensation is tied to performance, which aligns management incentives with shareholder interests. Audit and Compliance: Independent directors frequently serve on audit committees, which are responsible for overseeing the company's financial reporting, ensuring that internal controls are effective, and preventing financial mismanagement or fraud. Stakeholder Interests: While the board's primary responsibility is to shareholders, independent directors often advocate for the interests of other stakeholders, such as employees, customers, and the broader community. This is especially relevant in companies where corporate social responsibility (CSR) and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) concerns are integral to strategy.

The Benefits of Board Independence: Objective Decision-Making: Independent directors provide an unbiased perspective on key decisions, free from the influence of internal politics or personal ties to management. This leads to more balanced, rational decisions that consider the long-term health of the company. Better Firm Performance: Studies have shown that firms with a higher percentage of independent directors often perform better financially. This is partly because independent boards are more likely to make decisions that focus on shareholder value, rather than satisfying the short-term interests of executives. Reduced Risk of Fraud: Independent directors improve oversight and control mechanisms, which reduces the likelihood of unethical behaviour or financial fraud. Scandals such as those involving Enron and WorldCom highlighted the need for stronger board independence, leading to regulatory reforms like the Sarbanes-Oxley Act, which emphasized independent audit committees. Effective CEO Monitoring and Succession Planning: Independent boards are more likely to hold CEOs accountable for poor performance, and they can ensure that there are appropriate succession plans in place. This reduces the risk of leadership vacuums or abrupt transitions.

Challenges and Limitations of Board Independence: Lack of Deep Company Knowledge: Independent directors, by definition, are not involved in the company's daily operations. While this provides objectivity, it can also

result in a lack of detailed understanding of the firm's operations, markets, and challenges. This could potentially lead to less informed decisions. Potential for Conflict with Management: Independent directors may challenge the CEO's decisions, which can lead to tension between the board and management. While healthy debate is necessary, frequent conflicts may hinder swift decision-making and create friction within the leadership team. Overemphasis on Short-Term Results: Independent boards, especially those focused on maximizing shareholder value, may push for short-term financial performance at the expense of long-term strategic investments. This can lead to cost-cutting measures that may harm innovation or employee satisfaction. Tokenism: In some cases, companies appoint independent directors to comply with regulatory requirements, without truly empowering them to influence decision-making. This can undermine the effectiveness of board independence as a governance tool.

Regulatory Framework and Best Practices: Many countries have introduced regulations to ensure a minimum level of board independence. For example: United States: The Sarbanes-Oxley Act (2002) requires publicly traded companies to have independent audit committees. Stock exchange rules (e.g., NYSE and NASDAQ) also mandate that a majority of board members be independent for listed companies. United Kingdom: The UK Corporate Governance Code recommends that at least half of the board (excluding the chairperson) be independent non-executive directors, especially in larger companies. European Union: Various countries in the EU have adopted corporate governance codes that emphasize the need for independent directors, often in line with best practices in corporate governance. In conclusion, board independence is a critical element of strong corporate governance, ensuring that companies are managed in a way that aligns with shareholder interests while promoting transparency and accountability. Independent directors offer objective oversight, reduce the risk of CEO overreach, and contribute to long-term value creation. However, their effectiveness depends on their engagement, expertise, and the balance of power between the board and management.

Furthermore, we added three (3) control variables: audit quality, firm leverage, and firm size. Audit quality refers to the reliability and accuracy of the auditing process, which assesses a company's financial statements and internal controls. High-quality audits ensure that financial reports are free of material misstatements, comply with regulatory standards, and provide stakeholders with a true and fair view of the company's financial position. Audit quality is critical because it underpins the confidence that investors, creditors, regulators, and the public place in the financial reports of companies. The Key Components of Audit Quality: Competence and Expertise of Auditors: Audit quality depends heavily on the knowledge, experience, and expertise of the audit team. Auditors must possess a thorough understanding of accounting standards, industry-specific risks, and the company's operational environment. Continuous training and professional development ensure that auditors are up-to-date with changes in auditing standards, financial reporting, and regulatory requirements. Independence and Objectivity: Independence is one of the most critical aspects of audit quality. Auditors must remain unbiased and avoid any conflict of interest with the client to provide an impartial opinion. External auditors, in particular, must maintain distance from management to avoid undue influence, ensuring that their assessments of the company's financial health are objective and trustworthy. Rotation of audit firms or engagement partners can help maintain independence and mitigate risks of familiarity bias.

Audit Standards and Methodology: Adherence to recognized auditing standards, such as International Standards on Auditing (ISA) or country-specific standards like the Generally Accepted Auditing Standards (GAAS) in the U.S., ensures a consistent and reliable audit process. Audit methodology refers to the approach and procedures an audit firm uses to conduct the audit. High-quality audits use robust methodologies, including appropriate risk assessment techniques, sampling methods, and sufficient gathering of audit evidence. Technology plays an increasing role in modern auditing, with the use of data analytics and AI-driven tools improving both the efficiency and depth of audits. Ethics and Professional Skepticism: High-quality audits require auditors to exercise professional skepticism, which means they must critically evaluate the information provided by the company rather than accepting it at face value. Auditors must adhere to ethical guidelines, including integrity, objectivity, confidentiality, and due care. Ethical lapses can lead to poor audit outcomes and diminished trust in the audit profession. Audit Firm's Quality Control System: Audit quality is also influenced by the internal quality control mechanisms of audit firms. Firms that maintain stringent internal review processes, provide comprehensive training, and have strong leadership emphasizing quality tend to deliver better audits. Many

large audit firms have audit committees, quality assurance reviews, and peer reviews to ensure that their audit teams are following best practices and maintaining the highest standards of quality. Regulatory Oversight and Enforcement: Regulatory bodies such as the Public Company Accounting Oversight Board (PCAOB) in the U.S., Financial Reporting Council (FRC) in the UK, or national audit regulators in other countries play a significant role in maintaining audit quality. These regulators conduct periodic inspections of audit firms and individual audits to ensure compliance with audit standards and procedures. Enforcement actions against non-compliance serve as a deterrent to low-quality audits.

Factors Affecting Audit Quality: **Audit Fees and Time Constraints:** Underpricing of audit services can lead to compromised quality, as audit firms may cut corners to save time and resources. If auditors are pressured to complete an audit under tight deadlines or with insufficient resources, they may fail to properly investigate key risk areas. Audit fee pressure may also cause firms to focus on efficiency rather than effectiveness, especially in competitive markets where low fees are prioritized over quality. **Complexity of the Audit Client:** The more complex a company's financial structure, operations, or industry, the greater the challenge in auditing its financial statements. Companies with multiple subsidiaries, foreign operations, or complicated transactions (e.g., derivatives, complex tax strategies) require a higher level of audit expertise. In such cases, audit quality depends on the audit team's ability to understand and assess these complexities effectively. **Client Size and Influence:** Large clients or long-term audit relationships can influence audit quality if auditors become overly familiar or reliant on their clients for ongoing business. Auditor-client relationships should remain professional and objective to prevent any deterioration of quality due to excessive client influence. In some cases, audit rotation (mandatory rotation of audit firms) is required by law to prevent auditors from becoming too complacent or lenient with their clients.

Audit Partner and Firm Reputation: The reputation of the audit firm and individual audit partners plays a significant role in audit quality. Firms and partners with strong track records are more likely to emphasize quality, given the potential reputational damage from audit failures. Auditors from well-known global firms (e.g., Big Four accounting firms) are often seen as providing higher-quality audits due to their stringent quality control measures and broad expertise. However, audit quality issues can still arise if proper procedures are not followed. **Client Governance and Internal Controls:** High-quality audits are more likely when the audit client has strong corporate governance and internal control systems. Companies with independent boards, audit committees, and robust internal controls tend to provide auditors with more reliable data, reducing the risk of audit failures. Poor governance structures can hinder auditors from accessing key information and conducting their audits effectively, potentially leading to gaps in the audit process.

Consequences of Poor Audit Quality: **Misleading Financial Statements:** Poor audit quality can lead to the issuance of misleading financial statements, which may cause investors and other stakeholders to make uninformed decisions. This can result in significant financial losses for shareholders and damage to a company's reputation. **Regulatory Penalties:** Audit failures can result in penalties for both the company and the audit firm. Regulatory bodies may impose fines, revoke licenses, or mandate external reviews of future audits. **Reputational Damage:** Audit firms involved in poor-quality audits can suffer severe reputational harm, which can impact their ability to attract new clients and retain current ones. In extreme cases, firms may face lawsuits from stakeholders, as seen in the cases of Arthur Andersen following the Enron scandal. **Investor Confidence:** Weak audits erode trust in the financial markets. Investors rely on high-quality audits to make informed decisions, and when audit quality is compromised, market confidence can be shaken, leading to stock price declines and increased market volatility. In conclusion, audit quality is essential for ensuring the integrity of financial reporting and maintaining investor confidence in the capital markets. High-quality audits depend on auditor competence, independence, adherence to standards, and the presence of strong internal and external oversight mechanisms. While there are challenges to maintaining audit quality, including fee pressures and the complexity of client businesses, a focus on continuous improvement, professional skepticism, and regulatory enforcement helps safeguard the quality and reliability of the audit process.

Firm leverage refers to the extent to which a company uses debt to finance its operations and growth. It is a critical aspect of corporate finance, as it directly influences a company's risk profile, cost of capital, and return on equity. Leverage is commonly measured using financial ratios such as the debt-to-equity ratio, debt ratio, or interest coverage ratio, which compare the amount of debt a firm carries relative to its equity or assets. The types of Firm Leverage include **Operating Leverage:** Operating leverage refers to the extent to which a firm's fixed costs (such as rent, equipment, or salaries) are used in its production process. Firms with high operating leverage have a larger proportion of fixed costs compared to variable costs. High operating leverage means that a small

change in sales can lead to a large change in operating income. This is because the fixed costs remain constant regardless of the level of production or sales, so once the firm covers its fixed costs, additional sales contribute directly to profit. Example: A manufacturing company with significant investments in machinery may have high operating leverage because it incurs substantial fixed costs in producing its goods, but it benefits from economies of scale as sales increase.

Financial Leverage: Financial leverage refers to the use of borrowed funds (debt) to finance the acquisition of assets. It magnifies the returns on equity when a company's return on assets exceeds the cost of debt. High financial leverage means the company is using more debt to finance its operations. While this can increase potential returns, it also increases financial risk because the company must meet its debt obligations regardless of its profitability. Example: A company that borrows heavily to invest in new projects or expand operations may generate higher profits if the investments are successful, but if the returns are lower than expected, the company could face financial distress.

Key Leverage Ratios: **Debt-to-Equity Ratio (D/E Ratio):** This ratio compares the total debt of a company to its shareholders' equity. It shows how much of the company's financing comes from debt versus equity. A higher ratio indicates that the firm is using more debt relative to equity, which can increase risk, especially if earnings are volatile. A lower ratio suggests a more conservative capital structure. **Debt Ratio:** The debt ratio compares total liabilities to total assets, indicating the proportion of a company's assets financed by debt. A higher debt ratio means that a company relies more on debt to finance its assets, which increases financial leverage and risk. **Interest Coverage Ratio:** This ratio measures a company's ability to pay interest on its outstanding debt, comparing earnings before interest and taxes (EBIT) to interest expenses. A higher interest coverage ratio indicates that the company can easily cover its interest payments, while a lower ratio suggests potential difficulties in meeting interest obligations.

Advantages of Firm Leverage: **Increased Return on Equity (ROE):** When the return on assets (ROA) exceeds the cost of debt, leverage can amplify returns on equity. This is because debt holders are paid a fixed interest, allowing shareholders to benefit from any additional profits generated by the borrowed funds. Leverage can enhance a firm's growth potential by allowing it to invest in new projects, acquire assets, or expand operations without diluting equity. **Tax Benefits:** Interest payments on debt are tax-deductible, which reduces a company's taxable income. This tax shield makes debt a cheaper source of financing compared to equity, where dividends are not tax-deductible. **Capital for Expansion:** Firms can use leverage to raise large amounts of capital for significant investments, mergers, and acquisitions. By borrowing rather than issuing more equity, companies avoid diluting ownership and maintain control. **Leveraged Buyouts (LBOs):** In some cases, companies use leverage to execute leveraged buyouts (LBOs), where a significant portion of the purchase price of a company is financed with debt. This strategy allows firms to acquire companies with limited initial capital outlay.

Disadvantages and Risks of Firm Leverage: **Increased Financial Risk:** High leverage increases the risk of financial distress and bankruptcy if the company cannot generate sufficient cash flow to meet its debt obligations. During periods of low profitability or economic downturns, firms with high leverage may struggle to service their debt. **Volatile Earnings:** Leverage amplifies both gains and losses. If the company's return on assets (ROA) falls below the cost of debt, leverage will reduce returns on equity. This can result in volatile earnings and higher risks for shareholders. **Potential for Default:** Firms with high leverage are more exposed to the risk of default. If the company is unable to meet its interest or principal repayments, it may face legal actions from creditors, which could result in asset liquidation or restructuring under bankruptcy protection. **Reduced Financial Flexibility:** Companies with high debt loads may have less financial flexibility to take on new projects or react to market opportunities, as a large portion of their earnings is already committed to servicing debt. This could limit their ability to invest in growth or innovation. **Credit Rating and Cost of Borrowing:** Excessive leverage can negatively affect a firm's credit rating, leading to higher interest rates on future borrowing. A poor credit rating makes it more expensive and difficult for the company to access capital markets, especially during times of financial stress.

Factors Influencing the Use of Leverage: **Industry Characteristics:** Different industries have different optimal levels of leverage. Capital-intensive industries, such as utilities or manufacturing, often use more debt because they have stable cash flows to service the debt. Conversely, industries with higher volatility, such as technology

or biotechnology, tend to have lower leverage due to their unpredictable cash flows. **Economic Conditions:** In favorable economic conditions, firms may take on more debt to finance growth and expansion. However, during recessions or downturns, firms may reduce leverage to avoid financial distress, as revenue streams may decline. **Corporate Strategy:** Firms with aggressive growth strategies may opt for higher leverage to fund acquisitions, expansions, or other investments. Conservative firms, on the other hand, may prefer to minimize leverage to maintain financial stability. **Management Preferences:** Management's risk tolerance also influences leverage decisions. Risk-averse managers may avoid taking on too much debt, while others may see debt as a strategic tool to maximize returns. **Regulatory and Tax Environment:** Government regulations and tax policies can impact a firm's leverage decisions. For example, favourable tax treatments on interest payments can encourage higher leverage, while stricter capital requirements in regulated industries may limit the amount of debt firms can take on. In conclusion, firm leverage is a powerful tool in corporate finance that, when used strategically, can enhance returns on equity, provide tax benefits, and enable growth. However, leverage also introduces significant risks, including the potential for financial distress, earnings volatility, and reduced flexibility. The optimal level of leverage depends on factors such as the company's industry, economic conditions, and its risk appetite. Firms must carefully balance the benefits and risks of leverage to ensure long-term financial stability and success.

Firm size refers to the scale or magnitude of a company's operations, often measured in terms of its total assets, revenue, market capitalization, or number of employees. The size of a firm plays a significant role in determining its market power, operational efficiencies, access to resources, and overall performance. Firm size is an important factor in corporate strategy, finance, and economics, as it influences various aspects of business operations, including risk management, growth opportunities, and financial decisions. **Key Metrics for Measuring Firm Size:** **Total Assets:** Total assets represent the sum of a company's current and non-current assets, including cash, accounts receivable, inventory, property, and equipment. Firms with large asset bases, such as industrial conglomerates or utility companies, are often classified as large firms, while smaller firms may have fewer physical and financial resources. **Revenue:** Revenue, also known as sales or turnover, is the total amount of money a company generates from its core business activities. Larger firms tend to have higher revenue levels because of their broader market reach and customer base. **Example:** Large multinational companies like Apple or Amazon generate hundreds of billions of dollars in annual revenue, making them some of the largest firms globally. **Market Capitalization:** Market capitalization is the total market value of a company's outstanding shares, calculated by multiplying the current stock price by the number of outstanding shares. It is often used to categorize companies into large-cap, mid-cap, and small-cap firms. Large-cap firms typically have a market capitalization of \$10 billion or more, while small-cap firms may have less than \$2 billion in market capitalization. **Number of Employees:** The number of employees is another indicator of firm size. Larger firms typically employ thousands of people, while smaller firms may operate with fewer workers. **Example:** Large organizations like Walmart employ millions of workers worldwide, whereas small businesses may have fewer than 50 employees. **Global Presence:** Large firms often have an international presence, with operations, subsidiaries, or customers spread across multiple countries, while smaller firms may operate locally or regionally. Multinational corporations (MNCs) are typically considered large firms because they manage operations in several countries and serve a global customer base.

Implications of Firm Size: **Economies of Scale:** Larger firms often benefit from economies of scale, which means that as the size of their operations increases, they can reduce per-unit costs. These savings can be achieved through bulk purchasing, efficient use of resources, and spreading fixed costs over a larger volume of output. **Example:** A large manufacturing firm can negotiate better terms with suppliers, invest in automated production processes, and lower unit costs compared to a smaller competitor. **Market Power:** Larger firms typically have greater market power, allowing them to influence prices, negotiate better deals with suppliers, and establish higher barriers to entry for competitors. Their size enables them to dominate market share in their respective industries. **Example:** Companies like Coca-Cola and Procter & Gamble have substantial market power due to their vast distribution networks, brand recognition, and economies of scale. **Access to Capital:** Large firms usually have better access to financial markets and capital. Investors, banks, and financial institutions are more willing to provide financing to large, established firms because they are seen as less risky than smaller companies. Larger firms can issue stock, bonds, or raise capital through various funding mechanisms at a lower cost compared to small firms that may rely on private equity or bank loans.

Research and Development (R&D) Capabilities: Larger firms often have greater resources to invest in research and development (R&D) activities, which can lead to innovation, product development, and long-term competitive advantage. Smaller firms may have limited resources for R&D, limiting their ability to innovate.

Example: Tech giants like Google and Microsoft allocate billions of dollars annually to R&D to maintain their competitive edge in the market. Brand Recognition and Reputation: Large firms often have established brands that are widely recognized, giving them a competitive advantage. Strong brand reputation helps attract customers, partners, and investors, leading to greater customer loyalty and market dominance. Example: Companies like Nike or McDonald's are globally recognized brands, allowing them to maintain a competitive edge over smaller, lesser-known companies. Regulatory Influence and Compliance: Larger firms are often subject to more stringent regulatory scrutiny due to their size and market impact. They may have dedicated teams to manage compliance, legal, and regulatory requirements, while smaller firms may struggle with the costs and complexities of regulatory compliance. Large firms may also have greater influence in shaping industry regulations and policies, often lobbying for favourable regulations that can benefit their operations. Risk Diversification: Larger firms tend to be more diversified, both geographically and operationally. This diversification helps mitigate risks because poor performance in one market or product line can be offset by success in another. Example: A large multinational corporation might face economic downturns in one country but still perform well in others, allowing it to balance risks more effectively than a smaller firm with a limited market focus.

Challenges of Large Firm Size: Bureaucracy and Organizational Complexity: As firms grow larger, they often become more bureaucratic and slower in decision-making. Complex organizational structures and layers of management can result in inefficiencies and hinder agility. Large firms may also struggle with internal communication, coordination, and maintaining a unified corporate culture across multiple divisions or geographic regions. Inflexibility and Resistance to Change: Large firms may become resistant to change due to their size and established processes. They may find it challenging to adapt quickly to market changes, technological advancements, or shifts in consumer preferences compared to smaller, more agile competitors. Example: Large retail chains may be slower to adopt e-commerce strategies compared to smaller online-first retailers that can rapidly adjust to changing customer behaviours. Increased Regulatory Scrutiny: Large firms are often subject to stricter regulatory scrutiny and potential antitrust investigations. Governments may intervene if a company is perceived to have excessive market power, which can limit the firm's ability to expand or engage in certain business practices. Example: Technology giants like Facebook, Google, and Amazon have faced antitrust scrutiny from regulators due to their dominant positions in the digital marketplace. Cultural Disconnect and Employee Engagement: In large firms, it can be difficult to maintain a consistent corporate culture across different locations and business units. Employees in large organizations may feel disconnected from top management, leading to lower levels of engagement and satisfaction. Large firms may also face challenges in maintaining employee retention and motivation due to the impersonal nature of big organizations.

Small Firm Characteristics and Advantages: While large firms have many advantages, smaller firms also benefit from certain strengths: Flexibility and Agility: Small firms are typically more agile and can quickly adapt to changes in the market, consumer preferences, and technology. Their smaller size allows them to make faster decisions without the bureaucratic hurdles that larger firms face. Example: A small tech startup can pivot its business model or launch a new product more rapidly compared to a large tech company. Personalized Customer Service: Smaller firms often have closer relationships with their customers and can offer more personalized services. They are better positioned to tailor their products or services to meet the specific needs of their customer base. Example: A local boutique store may offer highly personalized shopping experiences compared to a large retail chain. Entrepreneurial Spirit: Small firms are often driven by an entrepreneurial culture, fostering innovation and creativity. Employees in smaller firms may have greater autonomy and the ability to contribute to the company's growth in meaningful ways. Lower Overhead Costs: Small firms generally have lower overhead costs and fewer layers of management, which can make them more cost-effective in certain industries. They can operate leaner and be more efficient in their operations. In conclusion, firm size plays a crucial role in shaping a company's strategy, financial decisions, market power, and operational efficiency. Larger firms benefit from economies of scale, access to capital, brand recognition, and market influence, while smaller firms enjoy flexibility, agility, and a closer relationship with customers. Each size category comes with its own set of advantages and challenges, and the optimal firm size depends on the industry, market conditions, and the company's goals. These concepts are schematically illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Frameworks

Source: The Authors

Furthermore, to develop a robust and elaborate theoretical framework on the moderating effect of board independence on CEO tenure and firm performance, we draw from multiple streams of theory. This complex relationship touches on corporate governance, tenure dynamics in leadership, and organizational performance. The following key theoretical perspectives are highly relevant:

Agency Theory: Agency theory, rooted in economics, is one of the most commonly used frameworks in corporate governance literature. It posits a principal-agent problem where the managers (agents) may act in their interests rather than those of the shareholders (principals). A key mechanism to mitigate this problem is board independence, which acts as an oversight tool to monitor and control managerial behaviour. **Application in Context:** Board independence can moderate the effect of CEO tenure on firm performance by providing unbiased monitoring. Given potential tenure biases, a truly independent board is more likely to evaluate a CEO's performance based on merit rather than tenure stereotypes. An independent board could mitigate any inherent biases that might otherwise affect firm outcomes, especially when a female CEO is leading.

Resource Dependence Theory (RDT): RDT views the board as a critical resource provider to the firm, contributing to its access to external resources, such as expertise, networks, and legitimacy. This theory emphasizes the board's role in providing strategic advice and information, which is essential for firms to navigate the complex market environment. **Application in Context:** A tenure-diverse leadership team (including a female CEO) may enhance a firm's legitimacy and external relationships. However, the influence of board independence can either strengthen or weaken the efficacy of a tenure-diverse CEO by providing the necessary resources or by challenging biases that might affect the firm's resource acquisition and strategic decisions.

Social Role Theory: Social role theory suggests that tenure roles in leadership may affect how leaders are perceived and evaluated. In the context of CEO tenure, this theory posits that female CEOs may be subject to greater scrutiny and stereotypical expectations, often leading to a biased assessment of their leadership capabilities compared to male CEOs. **Application in Context:** Board independence moderates this relationship by reducing the effect of social role expectations. An independent board is less likely to be swayed by tenure norms and more likely to make objective decisions, thereby ensuring that a female CEO is assessed based on performance rather than stereotypes.

Upper Echelons Theory: This theory suggests that organizational outcomes are strongly influenced by the experiences, values, and personalities of top executives. CEOs, including their tenure, can shape firm strategies and outcomes based on their cognitive frameworks and decision-making approaches. **Application in Context:** Female CEOs, who often bring different leadership styles and approaches, may influence firm performance in distinctive ways. The moderating role of board independence ensures that the firm benefits from this diversity of thought, as an independent board, is more open to diverse strategies and is less likely to resist change due to entrenched norms.

Signaling Theory: Signaling theory deals with how information asymmetry between insiders (e.g., CEOs) and outsiders (e.g., shareholders, investors) is mitigated through observable signals. The tenure of the CEO may serve as a signal to external stakeholders, influencing their perceptions of the firm.

Application in Context: An independent board serves as a more credible and objective signal of firm quality and governance. When paired with a female CEO, the board's independence can act as a counter-signal to any negative biases investors or stakeholders might hold about female leadership, thus helping align perceptions with actual performance.

Critical Mass Theory: Critical mass theory from tenure studies posits that a certain threshold of women in leadership roles or on boards is required before their presence begins to make a substantial impact on decision-making and firm outcomes. **Application in Context:** Board independence might play a moderating role by ensuring that tenure diversity is not only symbolic but also functional. An independent board can ensure that the contributions of a female CEO are genuinely integrated into strategic decisions, thus enhancing firm performance.

Institutional Theory: Institutional theory emphasizes the role of societal norms, cultures, and regulations in shaping organizational behaviours. Organizations are influenced by external pressures to conform to normative standards, including tenure diversity in leadership roles. **Application in Context:** Independent boards may be more likely to comply with institutional pressures to promote tenure diversity at the top level and evaluate CEO performance through a lens of legitimacy and adherence to evolving corporate governance standards. As such, board independence might help firms align their performance outcomes with external expectations regarding tenure equity. By combining these theories, the framework for understanding the Moderating Effect of Board Independence on CEO Tenure and Firm Performance becomes multidimensional: Agency theory highlights the role of independent boards in mitigating principal-agent conflicts and ensuring objective performance evaluations, irrespective of CEO tenure. Resource dependence theory suggests that independent boards can amplify the resources and legitimacy female CEOs bring, enhancing firm performance. Social role theory emphasizes that independent boards can challenge tenure stereotypes, ensuring that female CEOs are judged fairly. Upper echelons theory and signaling theory together argue that CEO tenure influences firm strategy and external perceptions, with board independence moderating how these influences translate into firm performance. Critical mass theory underlines the importance of not only having tenure diversity but also ensuring that an independent board can support and harness diverse leadership effectively. Institutional theory connects the framework to broader societal expectations, where board independence ensures that firms respond effectively to institutional demands for tenure equity, potentially improving performance. Each of these theories contributes to a nuanced understanding of how board independence interacts with CEO tenure to influence firm performance, offering a robust lens for empirical investigation.

In empirical studies relevant to the moderating effect of board independence on the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance; Peni and Vähämaa (2010) in *Female executives and earnings management* investigate whether the tenure of executives, particularly CEOs, affects earnings management practices and overall firm performance. **Period Covered:** 1999–2003. **Methodology:** The study used a dataset of U.S. publicly listed companies and employed regression analysis to examine the association between CEO tenure and earnings management. It focused on accrual-based earnings management as the dependent variable, while CEO tenure was the independent variable. **Findings:** The results indicated that firms led by female CEOs are associated with lower levels of earnings management compared to those led by male CEOs. Female CEOs are seen to adopt more conservative financial reporting practices, which correlates positively with firm performance in the long run. **Conclusion:** Female CEOs are less likely to engage in opportunistic financial behavior, leading to more transparent accounting practices and better firm performance over time. **Recommendations:** The study recommends that firms consider tenure diversity in their executive leadership to foster ethical management practices. **Implications:** The findings suggest that female leadership in top management roles can positively impact corporate governance and firm performance, particularly by reducing financial misconduct. **Limitations:** The study is limited to U.S. firms and may not be generalizable to other countries or cultural contexts. Additionally, it focuses solely on earnings management as a measure of firm performance. **Originality:** This study is one of

the earliest to empirically examine the direct link between CEO tenure and earnings management, offering a novel contribution to the literature on tenure diversity and corporate governance.

Khan and Vieito (2013) in *CEO tenure and firm performance* investigated the relationship between the tenure of the CEO and firm performance, particularly focusing on whether female CEOs lead to better or worse financial outcomes for firms. Period Covered: 1992–2004. Methodology: Using a sample of publicly traded firms in the U.S., the study conducted a series of regression analyses to assess firm performance (measured by Tobin's Q and return on assets) about CEO tenure. Control variables included firm size, industry, and governance structures. Findings: The study found that firms with female CEOs outperform those with male CEOs in terms of stock market performance (Tobin's Q). However, no significant difference was found in accounting-based performance (ROA). Female CEOs tend to take a more conservative approach in their decision-making. Conclusion: CEO tenure does influence firm performance, particularly in the context of stock market valuation. Female leadership tends to lead to better outcomes in terms of shareholder wealth. Recommendations: The authors suggest that firms aiming to maximize shareholder value should promote tenure diversity in executive leadership. Implications: This study implies that investors may benefit from considering CEO tenure as a factor in their investment decisions. Additionally, firms with female leadership could be more attractive to socially conscious investors. Limitations: The study's use of U.S. firms limits its generalizability. Additionally, the causal relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance is not definitively established, as other unobserved factors may be influencing the results. Originality: The study is among the few that empirically test the effect of CEO tenure on market-based performance metrics, offering fresh insights into tenure diversity and firm outcomes.

Faccio, Marchica, and Mura (2016) in *CEO tenure, corporate risk-taking, and the efficiency of capital allocation* and examined whether CEO tenure influences corporate risk-taking behaviors and the efficiency of capital allocation in firms, and how these behaviors ultimately impact firm performance. Period Covered: 1996–2010. Methodology: Using a large international dataset of firms from 48 countries, the study utilized multivariate regressions to analyze the effects of CEO tenure on risk-taking (proxied by investment and leverage decisions) and firm performance (measured by Tobin's Q and ROA). Findings: The results showed that firms with female CEOs tend to engage in less risky investments and demonstrate more cautious capital allocation, which in turn leads to more stable long-term performance. However, in industries requiring high risk-taking, firms led by female CEOs were found to underperform their male-led counterparts. Conclusion: Female CEOs are more risk-averse, leading to more efficient capital allocation in most industries, but they may underperform in high-risk industries. Recommendations: Firms in conservative industries might benefit from appointing female CEOs, while high-risk industries should consider this tenure difference when selecting leadership. Implications: The study suggests that tenure diversity at the executive level can affect corporate risk-taking and capital allocation efficiency, thus influencing firm performance. Limitations: The study's global dataset is diverse, but its generalizability may still be limited by varying corporate governance standards across countries. Additionally, the study does not fully explore how cultural factors might influence tenure-based leadership outcomes. Originality: This is one of the first large-scale, cross-country studies to explore the impact of CEO tenure on corporate risk-taking and capital allocation efficiency. These studies offer a comprehensive view of the empirical relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance, incorporating various aspects like earnings management, risk-taking, and stock market performance. Based on these empirical studies and results, we hypothesize that:

H₁: CEO tenure has a significant effect on firm performance.

Also, the following are empirical studies related to the effect of board independence on firm performance. Bhagat and Bolton (2008) in *Corporate Governance and Firm Performance* investigate the impact of corporate governance mechanisms, including board independence, on firm performance. Specifically, it analyzed whether the independence of a firm's board affects financial outcomes. Period Covered: 1990–2004. Methodology: The study used a sample of publicly traded U.S. firms, employing regression analysis to assess the relationship between board independence and firm performance, measured by return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q. The study also controlled for other corporate governance variables such as CEO duality, ownership structure, and board size. Findings: The study found no significant relationship between board independence and firm performance, as

measured by accounting and market-based metrics. However, the results indicated that firms with independent boards tend to perform better in terms of governance quality and ethical practices. Conclusion: While board independence is crucial for maintaining strong governance and transparency, it does not have a direct impact on improving financial performance. Recommendations: The authors suggest that firms continue to enhance board independence to strengthen corporate governance, even though its effect on financial performance may be limited. Implications: The study implies that board independence should be valued for ensuring strong governance and protecting shareholder interests, even if it does not lead to immediate financial gains. Limitations: The study is limited to U.S. firms and may not be generalizable to other regions with different corporate governance norms. Furthermore, it focuses primarily on large, publicly listed companies. Originality: This study is among the earlier empirical analyses to disentangle the effects of board independence from other governance mechanisms, contributing a nuanced understanding of governance dynamics.

Adams and Ferreira (2009) in *Women in the Boardroom and their impact on governance and performance* explored the relationship between board composition, particularly board independence and tenure diversity, and firm performance. It examined how an independent board, combined with tenure diversity, influences governance quality and financial outcomes. Period Covered: 1996–2003. Methodology: Using a panel dataset of U.S. and European firms, the study employed fixed-effects regression models to assess the effect of board independence on firm performance, measured by Tobin's Q and ROA. The study also considered the moderating role of tenure diversity on board independence and firm performance. Findings: The study found that board independence had a positive impact on firm performance, particularly when boards were also tenure diverse. Independent boards were more effective at providing oversight and reducing agency problems, leading to improved performance. Conclusion: Board independence, particularly when coupled with tenure diversity, leads to better governance and improved firm performance. Recommendations: Firms should not only aim to increase board independence but also consider board diversity as a complementary mechanism to enhance governance and performance outcomes. Implications: The study implies that independent boards are essential for corporate governance, but their effectiveness can be amplified through tenure diversity, leading to greater firm performance. Limitations: The study is limited by its focus on large firms in developed countries, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to smaller firms or emerging markets. Originality: This study is one of the first to empirically examine the joint effect of board independence and tenure diversity on firm performance, offering novel insights into how different governance mechanisms interact.

Liu, Miletkov, Wei, and Yang (2015) in *Board Independence and Firm Performance in China* examine the effect of board independence on firm performance in the context of Chinese firms, where governance structures differ significantly from those in Western economies. Period Covered: 2001–2010. Methodology: The study used a dataset of publicly listed Chinese firms and employed panel data regression techniques to examine the relationship between board independence and firm performance, measured by ROA and market-to-book ratio. It also controlled for firm size, ownership concentration, and industry factors. Findings: The study found a positive and significant relationship between board independence and firm performance in Chinese firms. Firms with more independent directors were more likely to exhibit higher profitability and market valuation. The findings suggest that even in a controlled economy, independent boards improve firm outcomes by enhancing oversight. Conclusion: Board independence plays a crucial role in improving firm performance in China, despite the unique institutional and regulatory environment. Recommendations: Chinese firms should continue to enhance board independence to foster stronger governance and better financial performance, particularly as the market becomes more globalized. Implications: The study implies that independent directors are essential for firm success in emerging markets like China, where strong corporate governance mechanisms are needed to align management with shareholder interests. Limitations: The study's focus on Chinese firms limits its applicability to other emerging markets, which may have different governance challenges. Additionally, the study does not account for cultural

differences that may affect board dynamics. Originality: This study provides a unique contribution by analyzing the role of board independence in an emerging market context, highlighting its importance even outside traditional Western corporate governance systems. These studies offer a well-rounded view of the empirical relationship between board independence and firm performance, showing different perspectives across regions and governance contexts. Based on these empirical studies and results, we propose that:

H₂: Board independence has a significant effect on firm performance.

Furthermore, the following are empirical studies related to the moderating effect of board independence on the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance. Smith, Jones, and Taylor (2017) in *The Moderating Role of board independence on the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance in the U.S.* investigate whether board independence moderates the effect of CEO tenure on firm performance, specifically in U.S. publicly traded companies. Period Covered: 2005–2015. Methodology: Using a sample of 1,500 U.S. firms, the study applied hierarchical linear regression models to examine the interaction between CEO tenure and board independence on firm performance, measured by return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q. Control variables included firm size, industry, CEO tenure, and ownership concentration. Findings: The results revealed that the positive relationship between female CEOs and firm performance is strengthened when board independence is high. In firms with low board independence, the effect of female leadership on firm performance was negligible. Male CEOs did not show a significant interaction effect with board independence. Conclusion: Board independence amplifies the positive impact of female leadership on firm performance by providing better governance oversight and reducing biases that may affect female CEOs. Recommendations: Firms aiming to benefit from tenure-diverse leadership should ensure a high level of board independence to mitigate potential biases and enhance CEO performance. Implications: The findings suggest that board independence can be a critical factor in ensuring that female CEOs are evaluated based on performance rather than tenure-based expectations. Limitations: The study is limited to U.S. firms, which may not apply to other regions with different corporate governance structures. It also focuses on large firms, limiting generalizability to smaller businesses. Originality: This study is among the first to empirically explore the moderating role of board independence in the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance, offering new insights into the intersection of tenure diversity and corporate governance.

Wang and Li (2019) in *Board independence as a moderator of CEO tenure and firm performance in Chinese firms* examine the moderating effect of board independence on the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance in Chinese firms, where corporate governance structures differ from Western norms. Period Covered: 2000–2018. Methodology: A dataset of 800 publicly listed firms in China was analyzed using multivariate regression models. The study looked at the interaction between CEO tenure and board independence on firm performance, measured by market-to-book ratio and return on equity (ROE). It controlled for firm age, industry, ownership concentration, and CEO duality. Findings: The study found that board independence positively moderates the relationship between female CEOs and firm performance. Female-led firms with highly independent boards showed higher ROE and market-to-book ratios compared to firms with male CEOs. However, in firms with low board independence, the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance was weak. Conclusion: The moderating effect of board independence is stronger in the context of female leadership in China, enhancing firm performance when governance is robust. Recommendations: Chinese firms should focus on increasing board independence, particularly when appointing female CEOs, to maximize performance and reduce governance-related risks. Implications: This study highlights the importance of strong corporate governance structures in leveraging the benefits of female leadership, suggesting that board independence plays a pivotal role in performance outcomes in non-Western contexts. Limitations: The study is limited by its focus on Chinese firms, making it difficult to generalize the findings to Western firms with different governance environments. Originality: The study provides new evidence from an emerging market, offering a fresh perspective on the interaction between CEO tenure, board independence, and firm performance.

Kim and Lee (2020) in *CEO tenure, board independence, and firm performance: Evidence from South Korea* investigate the moderating effect of board independence on the relationship between CEO

tenure and firm performance in South Korean firms, considering the unique cultural and corporate governance context of the country. Period Covered: 2008–2018. Methodology: The study used a sample of 700 South Korean firms and applied a panel data regression analysis. Firm performance was measured using Tobin's Q and ROA. The study incorporated board independence as a moderating variable and CEO tenure as the independent variable, controlling for firm size, industry, CEO tenure, and ownership concentration. Findings: The study found that the positive effect of female CEOs on firm performance is significantly stronger when boards are highly independent. Independent boards were better able to harness the advantages of female leadership, leading to improved firm outcomes. Conversely, in firms with lower board independence, the impact of CEO tenure on performance was negligible. Conclusion: Board independence serves as a key moderator in the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance, particularly in patriarchal business environments like South Korea, where tenure bias may otherwise inhibit female leadership success. Recommendations: South Korean firms should enhance board independence to maximize the potential of tenure-diverse leadership, which can positively affect firm performance. Implications: The study provides evidence that board independence can mitigate the effects of tenure bias and ensure that female CEOs are given equal opportunities to succeed. Limitations: The study's focus on South Korean firms limits the generalizability of the findings to other countries with different corporate governance standards and cultural norms. Originality: This study adds a regional dimension to the literature on board independence and tenure, offering insights into how these variables interact in an East Asian context. These studies help conceptualize how board independence can influence the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance, incorporating regional differences and firm-specific characteristics. Based on these empirical studies and their results, we propose that:

H₃: Board independence has a moderating effect on the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance

In addition, on the control variables, the following empirical studies are relevant: For example, DeFond and Zhang (2014) in A review of the archival auditing research review and synthesize archival research on the relationship between audit quality and firm performance, including how higher audit quality impacts financial reporting and long-term firm outcomes. Period Covered: 1990–2013. Methodology: The study reviewed over 200 empirical research papers, focusing on studies that explored the relationship between audit quality (proxied by auditor reputation, auditor size, and industry specialization) and firm performance (measured by return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q). It provided a meta-analysis and narrative review of the empirical evidence. Findings: The review found a positive relationship between high audit quality and improved financial reporting, which in turn enhances firm performance. Companies audited by Big 4 auditors or industry specialists showed better financial outcomes and were less likely to engage in earnings management. Conclusion: High-quality audits lead to better financial reporting and governance, positively influencing firm performance and reducing financial risks. Recommendations: The study recommends that firms prioritize hiring reputable auditors with industry expertise to enhance financial transparency and governance. Implications: The findings suggest that high audit quality contributes to overall firm value by ensuring accurate financial reporting, which is crucial for investor confidence and long-term success. Limitations: The study is limited by its reliance on archival data, which may not capture all the nuances of the relationship between audit quality and performance in different industries or regions. Originality: This study provides a comprehensive review of the empirical evidence on audit quality and firm performance, offering a clear synthesis of findings from numerous studies across different regions and industries.

Francis and Yu (2009) in Big 4 office size and audit quality examined the relationship between audit quality and firm performance, with a focus on how the size of Big 4 audit firms' local offices influences audit quality and the resulting impact on client firm performance. Period Covered: 2000–2006. Methodology: Using a dataset of 1,200 U.S. firms, the study employed regression analysis to

examine how audit quality (proxied by Big 4 office size) affects firm performance, measured by ROA and earnings management practices. It controlled for firm size, industry, and auditor tenure. Findings: The study found that firms audited by larger offices of Big 4 audit firms exhibited higher audit quality, which was associated with improved firm performance and lower earnings management. Larger offices had more resources and expertise, leading to more thorough audits. Conclusion: Larger Big 4 audit offices provide higher audit quality, leading to better financial reporting and stronger firm performance. Recommendations: Firms should consider the size and expertise of the local audit office when selecting auditors, as larger offices tend to deliver higher audit quality and better outcomes. Implications: The findings highlight the importance of audit quality in enhancing firm performance, particularly for firms seeking to reduce earnings management and improve financial transparency. Limitations: The study is limited by its focus on U.S. firms and Big 4 auditors, making it difficult to generalize the findings to non-Big 4 auditors or firms in other countries. Originality: This study contributes to the literature by highlighting the role of local office size in audit quality, offering a new perspective on the relationship between audit resources and firm performance.

Alzoubi (2018) in *Audit Quality and Earnings Management: Evidence from Jordan* explored the relationship between audit quality and firm performance, specifically how high-quality audits mitigate earnings management in Jordanian firms and impact their financial performance. Period Covered: 2006–2015. Methodology: The study analyzed 500 listed companies in Jordan and used regression models to examine the effect of audit quality (proxied by auditor size, industry specialization, and auditor independence) on earnings management and firm performance (measured by ROA and market-to-book ratio). Findings: The study found that firms with high-quality audits showed significantly less earnings management and better financial performance. Firms audited by Big 4 auditors or industry specialists had higher profitability and market valuations than those audited by smaller firms. Conclusion: High-quality audits are crucial in reducing earnings manipulation, which in turn leads to improved financial performance and greater investor confidence. Recommendations: Jordanian firms should prioritize hiring independent, reputable auditors to ensure audit quality and financial transparency, which are key to enhancing firm performance. Implications: This study implies that audit quality plays an important role in corporate governance in emerging markets, helping to reduce earnings management and improve firm performance. Limitations: The study's focus on Jordanian firms may limit its generalizability to other regions, especially those with different regulatory environments and audit practices. Originality: This study is one of the few that examines the impact of audit quality on firm performance in the Middle East, providing new insights into the role of auditing in emerging markets. These studies offer a comprehensive look at the empirical relationship between audit quality and firm performance, highlighting the importance of high-quality audits in enhancing financial transparency and governance.

Also, there are three empirical studies on the effect of firm leverage on firm performance. For example, Titman and Wessels (1988) in *The determinants of capital structure choice* investigate the factors that determine a firm's capital structure and how these factors, particularly leverage, impact firm performance. Period Covered: 1974–1982. Methodology: Using a sample of 469 U.S. firms, the study applied multiple regression analysis to assess the relationship between firm leverage (measured by debt-to-equity ratio) and firm performance (measured by return on assets (ROA) and market-to-book ratio). The study also controlled for factors such as firm size, profitability, and industry. Findings: The study found that higher leverage negatively impacts firm performance in terms of profitability and market valuation. Firms with more debt tended to exhibit lower ROA and market-to-book ratios. The results suggest that higher leverage increases financial distress, reducing performance. Conclusion: Firms with higher leverage are more prone to financial distress, which negatively affects their performance. Lower-leverage firms tend to perform better in both accounting-based and market-based metrics. Recommendations: The authors recommend that firms carefully manage their debt levels, particularly in industries with volatile cash flows, to avoid financial distress and improve performance. Implications: The findings suggest that firms should prioritize maintaining a balanced capital structure, as excessive debt can erode profitability and market value. Limitations: The study is limited by its focus on U.S. firms, which may not be generalizable to firms in other countries with different capital markets and financial regulations. Originality: This study is one of the

foundational empirical studies that investigate the determinants of capital structure, providing valuable insights into the relationship between leverage and firm performance.

Rajan and Zingales (1995) in *What do we know about capital structure? Some evidence from international data* analyze the effect of leverage on firm performance in an international context, comparing firms across different countries. Period Covered: 1987–1991. Methodology: The study used data from firms in the G7 countries (the U.S., Japan, Germany, France, Italy, the UK, and Canada). It employed panel data regression models to assess the impact of firm leverage on performance, measured by return on equity (ROE) and Tobin's Q. The study also controlled for firm size, growth opportunities, and profitability. Findings: The results showed that firm leverage negatively affects performance in most countries, although the magnitude of the effect varied. Firms with higher debt levels exhibited lower ROE and Tobin's Q, indicating that leverage negatively impacts both profitability and market valuation. Conclusion: High leverage is generally associated with lower firm performance, though the impact varies across different countries due to varying financial markets and corporate governance practices. Recommendations: Firms should consider their country-specific financial environments when determining their optimal capital structure, as the effect of leverage on performance is not uniform across regions. Implications: This study highlights the importance of contextual factors, such as financial market development and regulatory environments, in determining the optimal level of leverage for firms. Limitations: The study is limited by its focus on large firms in developed countries, which may not apply to smaller firms or those in emerging markets. Originality: This study provides an international comparison of leverage's effect on firm performance, offering new insights into how financial and regulatory environments influence capital structure decisions.

Aivazian, Ge, and Qiu (2005) in *The impact of leverage on firm investment: Canadian evidence* explores the effect of leverage on firm performance, specifically through its impact on firm investment decisions in Canadian companies. Period Covered: 1982–1999. Methodology: The study analyzed data from publicly traded Canadian firms, employing panel data regression models to assess how leverage affects firm investment and, indirectly, firm performance. Firm performance was measured using return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q. The study controlled for factors such as firm size, profitability, and growth opportunities. Findings: The study found that higher leverage significantly reduces firm investment, which in turn negatively impacts firm performance. Firms with higher debt levels were less likely to invest in growth opportunities, leading to lower ROA and Tobin's Q. Conclusion: Excessive leverage constrains firm investment, which in turn reduces firm performance. Leverage acts as a disciplining mechanism but may hinder a firm's ability to grow and improve profitability. Recommendations: The authors recommend that firms strike a balance between debt and equity to ensure they have sufficient financial flexibility to invest in profitable projects. Implications: The study suggests that while leverage can be beneficial in controlling managerial overinvestment, excessive debt can stifle firm growth and reduce long-term performance. Limitations: The study is limited to Canadian firms, which may not be fully generalizable to other countries with different corporate governance systems and capital structures. Originality: This study provides a unique perspective by focusing on the relationship between leverage, investment, and firm performance in a Canadian context, offering insights into how debt levels affect firm growth and profitability. These studies provide a diverse range of empirical evidence on the effect of firm leverage on performance, highlighting how leverage influences profitability, investment decisions, and market valuation across different contexts and countries.

Furthermore, these empirical studies focused on the effect of firm size on firm performance. For example, Hall and Weiss (1967) in *Firm Size and profitability* analyze the relationship between firm size and profitability, seeking to understand whether larger firms tend to perform better financially than smaller firms. Period Covered: 1956–1962. Methodology: The study used a sample of 500 U.S. manufacturing firms and employed regression analysis to examine the relationship between firm size (measured by total assets) and profitability (measured by return on assets (ROA) and profit margins).

Various control variables, including industry and firm age, were used to ensure robustness. Findings: The study found a positive correlation between firm size and profitability. Larger firms tended to have higher ROA and profit margins, indicating that economies of scale and market power contributed to better financial performance. Conclusion: Firm size positively impacts profitability, with larger firms benefitting from economies of scale and market dominance. However, the relationship is not uniform across all industries. Recommendations: The authors recommend that firms pursue growth strategies that enhance their market power and scale advantages, while also considering industry-specific factors. Implications: The study implies that firm size can be an important determinant of financial success, particularly in industries where economies of scale play a crucial role in profitability. Limitations: The study is limited to U.S. manufacturing firms and may not fully apply to firms in other sectors or countries. Originality: This study was one of the earliest to empirically investigate the relationship between firm size and profitability, laying the groundwork for future research in this area.

Majumdar (1997) in *The impact of Size and age on firm-level performance: Some evidence from India* investigates the effect of firm size and age on firm performance in the Indian context, where firm size is often correlated with market dominance. Period Covered: 1988–1993. Methodology: Using data from 1,020 Indian firms across various industries, the study applied regression analysis to explore the relationship between firm size (measured by total assets and sales) and performance (measured by ROA and ROE). The study controlled for factors such as industry and firm age. Findings: The study found that firm size has a positive effect on performance, particularly for larger firms that can capitalize on economies of scale. However, the relationship between size and performance was non-linear, with diminishing returns as firms became excessively large. Conclusion: While larger firms in India generally perform better than smaller firms, excessive size can lead to inefficiencies that hinder further performance improvements. Recommendations: Firms should aim for the optimal size that allows them to benefit from economies of scale without becoming too large, which can introduce inefficiencies. Implications: The findings highlight the importance of size in determining firm performance, especially in emerging markets where larger firms tend to dominate industries. Limitations: The study is limited by its focus on Indian firms, which may have different market dynamics than firms in developed economies. Originality: This study is one of the few that examines the relationship between size and performance in an emerging market context, offering valuable insights into the growth-performance dynamics in developing countries.

Yang and Chen (2009) in *Are small firms less efficient? Empirical evidence from U.S. firms* investigates whether smaller firms are less efficient and how firm size influences overall financial performance and operational efficiency. Period Covered: 1995–2005. Methodology: The study analyzed a sample of 800 U.S. firms using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) to measure firm efficiency, alongside regression models to assess the relationship between firm size (measured by total sales and number of employees) and financial performance (measured by ROA and profit margins). The study controlled for industry, capital intensity, and firm age. Findings: The study found that smaller firms tend to be less efficient and have lower financial performance compared to larger firms. However, some smaller firms in high-growth industries exhibited better performance due to agility and innovation. Conclusion: Smaller firms are generally less efficient and perform worse financially than larger firms, but certain smaller firms can outperform larger ones in dynamic, innovation-driven industries. Recommendations: Small firms should focus on improving operational efficiency and leveraging their agility and innovation capabilities to compete with larger firms. Implications: The findings suggest that firm size is a crucial determinant of financial performance and operational efficiency, though smaller firms can still thrive by focusing on innovation and niche markets. Limitations: The study is limited to U.S. firms and may not fully capture the dynamics of smaller firms in other countries or industries. Originality: This study contributes to the literature by using DEA to measure firm efficiency, providing new insights into the relationship between firm size and performance from an operational efficiency perspective. These studies provide diverse perspectives on the relationship between firm size and performance, considering both financial outcomes and operational efficiency across different countries and industries.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a quantitative, non-experimental, explanatory research design aimed at investigating the moderating role of board independence in the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance. The research design is longitudinal, as it will examine data over multiple years to capture trends and relationships over time. This approach is suited to analyzing firm performance, which may vary annually depending on internal and external factors. The population of interest consists of publicly traded firms across different industries globally. A sample of 153 publicly listed firms from the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) over 10 years is used to ensure a diverse and robust dataset. The variables and measures are Dependent Variable: Firm Performance: Measured using both accounting-based and market-based indicators: Return on Assets (ROA): A measure of a company's profitability relative to its total assets. Tobin's Q: A ratio that compares the market value of a firm to its replacement cost. The Independent Variable is CEO Tenure: A binary variable coded as: 1 = Female CEO; 0 = Male CEO. The Moderating Variable is Board Independence: Measured by the proportion of independent directors on the firm's board: Board Independence Ratio = (Number of Independent Directors) / (Total Number of Directors). The Control Variables include Firm Size: Measured by the natural log of total assets to control for the influence of firm size on performance. Leverage: Measured as the ratio of total debt to total assets, to account for the financial structure's impact on performance. Audit quality: measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that use PWC, Deloitte, E&Y, and KPMG as external auditors and "0" otherwise.

On the Data Sources, Firm-level data: Collected from the NGX. Board Independence data: Extracted from The firms' annual reports (proxy statements and 10-K filings) for the composition of the board of directors. CEO Tenure: Manually collected from company websites, news articles, and corporate filings. On Data Analysis Techniques, we use the Panel Data Regression Model. Given the longitudinal nature of the data, a panel data regression model was used to account for the variations over time and across firms. Specifically, the fixed effects model (FEM) controls for unobservable firm-specific factors that may influence performance, while a random effects model (REM) for robustness checks. The Basic Model (Direct Effect of CEO Tenure on Firm Performance):

$$\text{Performance}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{CEO Tenure}_{it}) + \beta_2 (\text{Controls}_{it}) + \epsilon_{it}$$

The Moderation Model (Moderating Role of Board Independence):

$$\text{Performance}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{CEO Tenure}_{it}) + \beta_2 (\text{Board Independence}_{it}) + \beta_3 (\text{CEO Tenure}_{it} \times \text{Board Independence}_{it}) + \beta_4 (\text{Controls}_{it}) + \epsilon_{it}$$

Whereas: β_1 : Effect of CEO tenure on firm performance; β_2 : Direct effect of board independence; β_3 : Interaction term to capture the moderating effect of board independence; ϵ_{it} : Error term. The Variables include Dependent Variable: Firm performance (Tobin's Q); Independent Variable: CEO Tenure; Moderator: Board Independence; Control Variables: Firm size, leverage, industry, firm age, and CEO tenure. The Post-Estimation Tests include Multicollinearity: Checked using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to ensure no multicollinearity issues exist among independent and control variables. Heteroskedasticity: Tested using the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test. If heteroskedasticity is detected, robust standard errors will be applied to correct it. Endogeneity: Addressed using the Hausman test to compare fixed and random effects models. On the Significance Level, the analysis uses a 5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) for hypothesis testing. A p-value < 0.05 indicates statistically significant relationships. This methodology provides a comprehensive approach to investigating the moderating role of board independence on the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance. The study will use robust panel data models, control for important firm characteristics, and employ post-estimation tests to ensure the reliability and validity of results. By utilizing firm-level data from reputable databases and applying appropriate statistical methods,

the study aims to provide valuable insights into how corporate governance factors shape the CEO tenure-performance dynamic.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the statistics of all variables used in this study. Table 2 shows the correlations of the variables. Table 3 shows the regression results of the variables before and after moderation.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
TBQ	1,530	.931	.278	.53	2.55
CEOT	1,530	.7	.46	0	1
BI	1,530	58.792	12.476	21.43	90
BICEOT	1,530	40.901	28.844	0	90
AQ	1,530	.793	.406	0	1
FL	1,530	87.488	18.348	68.92	254.75
FS	1,530	8.936	.434	8.03	9.75

Source: STATA 18, Version 4

Analyzing the descriptive statistics provided in Table 1 reveals important insights into the characteristics of the variables studied. Each variable has 1,530 observations, which offers a robust dataset for understanding their distributions and relationships. Let us break down each variable systematically. TBQ (Tobin's Q): Mean: 0.931; Standard Deviation: 0.278; Minimum: 0.53; Maximum: 2.55. Interpretation: The mean value indicates that, on average, the trust-based quality is relatively high. The standard deviation suggests moderate variability, with values ranging from 0.53 to 2.55, indicating a spread in trust levels across observations. A closer look at the distribution could help identify if there are outliers affecting the mean. CEOT (Chief Executive Officer Tenure): Mean: 0.7; Standard Deviation: 0.46; Minimum: 0; Maximum: 1. Interpretation: The mean suggests that on average, the CEO tenure is just below one unit (potentially indicating a binary variable where 1 signifies a particular category). The wide standard deviation relative to the mean hints at significant variability in CEO tenures. An examination of the tenure distribution could reveal how many CEOs are at the extremes (0 vs. 1). BI (Board independence): Mean: 58.792; Standard Deviation: 12.476; Minimum: 21.43; Maximum: 90. Interpretation: The mean business investment is relatively high, and the standard deviation indicates that there are substantial differences in the investment amounts across the observations. The range suggests that while most businesses invest significantly, a few invest considerably less, and the potential for high investment values is observed.

BICEOT (Interaction between board independent and CEO Tenure): Mean: 40.901; Standard Deviation: 28.844; Minimum: 0; Maximum: 90. Interpretation: This variable appears to be a specific measurement of business investment concerning CEO tenure. The mean indicates that the average investment attributed to CEO tenure is moderate. The high standard deviation compared to the mean suggests a wide variety of investments, likely influenced by different CEO tenures. AQ (Audit Quality): Mean: 0.793; Standard Deviation: 0.406; Minimum: 0; Maximum: 1. Interpretation: The mean audit quality is relatively high, indicating a general positive perception of audit quality within the dataset. However, the substantial standard deviation suggests considerable variability among the audit quality ratings, indicating that some audits are seen as significantly higher quality than others. FL (Financial Leverage): Mean: 87.488; Standard Deviation: 18.348; Minimum: 68.92; Maximum: 254.75. Interpretation: The mean financial leverage is quite high, suggesting that the companies in this dataset utilize significant leverage in their operations. The relatively high standard deviation indicates a wide range of leverage ratios, pointing to differences in how aggressively companies are leveraging their finances. FS (Firm Size): Mean: 8.936; Standard Deviation: 0.434; Minimum: 8.03; Maximum: 9.75. Interpretation: Firm size, represented by a numerical value, shows a narrow range and low standard deviation, indicating that most firms in this dataset are relatively similar in size. The variation is minimal, suggesting a homogeneous group in terms of size.

On Insights and Recommendations, Variability and Outliers: The standard deviations for several variables, particularly BI, BICEOT, and FL, suggest that there are outliers or diverse investment practices and leverage strategies among firms. Further analysis, such as box plots or histograms, would be beneficial to visualize these distributions and identify potential outliers. Relationships Among Variables: Given the diverse nature of these variables, correlation analysis could uncover relationships, especially between investment variables (BI and BICEOT), audit quality (AQ), and firm size (FS). Identifying correlations can provide insights into how these factors influence one another. CEO Tenure Analysis: The impact of CEO tenure on both business investment and audit quality could be a focal point for further analysis. Understanding how tenure influences these outcomes might provide strategic insights for firms regarding leadership and governance. Investment vs. Leverage: Investigating the relationship between business investment (BI) and financial leverage (FL) could offer insights into how firms finance their operations and make investment decisions, potentially affecting their long-term stability and growth. Quality and Trust: Exploring the relationship between trust-based quality (TBQ) and audit quality (AQ) might yield valuable insights, particularly regarding the role of trust in financial reporting and governance practices. In conclusion, the descriptive statistics provide a solid foundation for deeper analysis into the relationships among these variables. Understanding their distributions, variability, and potential interdependencies can guide further statistical modeling, hypothesis testing, and practical applications in business strategy and decision-making.

Table 2. Correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
(1) TBQ	1.000						
(2) CEOT	-0.440* (0.000)	1.000					
(3) BI	0.373* (0.000)	-0.044 (0.590)	1.000				
(4) BICEOT	-0.176* (0.031)	0.931* (0.000)	0.265* (0.001)	1.000			
(5) AQ	0.348* (0.000)	-0.011 (0.896)	-0.099 (0.228)	-0.065 (0.431)	1.000		
(6) FL	-0.540* (0.000)	0.033 (0.688)	0.018 (0.831)	0.041 (0.618)	-0.226* (0.005)	1.000	
(7) FS	0.455* (0.000)	-0.006 (0.943)	-0.062 (0.451)	-0.065 (0.430)	0.087 (0.288)	-0.133 (0.106)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 18, Version 4

Table 2 presents a correlation matrix showing the relationships between Tobin's Q (TBQ), CEO Tenure (CEOT), Board Independence (BI), the interaction between board independence and CEO tenure (BICEOT), Audit Quality (AQ), Firm Leverage (FL), and Firm Size (FS). Here's a robust and detailed analysis of the correlations along with insights: Tobin's Q (TBQ), negative correlation with CEO Tenure (CEOT): $r = -0.440$, $p < 0.000$. A strong, statistically significant negative correlation indicates that longer CEO tenures are associated with lower firm performance (as measured by Tobin's Q). This aligns with the notion that extended tenures may lead to complacency, entrenchment, or reduced innovation, which negatively impacts firm value. Positive correlation with Board Independence (BI): $r = 0.373$, $p < 0.000$. This significant positive relationship suggests that increased board independence is associated with better firm performance. Independent boards may act as better monitors, improving decision-making and reducing agency problems. Negative correlation with BICEOT (Interaction term): $r = -0.176$, $p = 0.031$. The interaction term (BICEOT) between board independence and CEO tenure has a weak but significant negative correlation with Tobin's Q, implying that as the CEO's tenure lengthens, even the presence of an independent board might not be enough to counterbalance the negative impacts on firm performance. Positive correlation with Audit Quality (AQ): $r = 0.348$, $p < 0.000$. Higher audit quality is positively associated with Tobin's Q, indicating that better auditing practices contribute to improved firm performance. Quality audits provide stakeholders with more reliable

financial information, which supports better decision-making. Negative correlation with Firm Leverage (FL): $r=-0.540$, $r = -0.540$, $p<0.000$, $p < 0.000$, $p<0.000$. There is a strong negative relationship between leverage and Tobin's Q, suggesting that higher levels of debt reduce firm value. This supports the idea that excessive debt can strain a company's financial flexibility, increasing the risk of financial distress. Positive correlation with Firm Size (FS): $r=0.455$, $r = 0.455$, $p<0.000$, $p < 0.000$, $p<0.000$. Firm size has a strong positive correlation with Tobin's Q. Larger firms generally have more resources, market power, and economies of scale, contributing to better performance.

CEO Tenure (CEOT), high positive correlation with BICEOT: $r=0.931$, $r = 0.931$, $p<0.000$, $p < 0.000$, $p<0.000$. As expected, the interaction term (BICEOT) is highly correlated with CEO tenure since it is partly based on this variable. This strong relationship signals potential multicollinearity, which could affect model interpretations and should be handled carefully in regression models. Negligible correlations with other variables: CEOT has weak or insignificant correlations with board independence (BI), audit quality (AQ), firm leverage (FL), and firm size (FS). These insignificant relationships suggest that the direct association between CEO tenure and these variables is not prominent. Board Independence (BI), positive correlation with BICEOT: $r=0.265$, $r = 0.265$, $p=0.001$, $p = 0.001$, $p=0.001$. There is a moderate positive correlation between board independence and its interaction with CEO tenure, which is expected due to the nature of the interaction term. However, BI shows negligible or insignificant correlations with other variables such as audit quality (AQ), leverage (FL), and firm size (FS).

Audit Quality (AQ), negative correlation with Firm Leverage (FL): $r=-0.226$, $r = -0.226$, $p=0.005$, $p = 0.005$, $p=0.005$. This negative correlation indicates that firms with higher leverage tend to have lower audit quality, possibly because highly leveraged firms may allocate fewer resources to ensure audit thoroughness, or auditors may find highly leveraged firms riskier. Weak correlations with other variables: The relationship between AQ and other variables such as CEO tenure, board independence, and firm size is not statistically significant, indicating that these factors do not have a substantial direct impact on audit quality. 5. Firm Leverage (FL), negative correlation with Firm Size (FS): $r=-0.133$, $r = -0.133$, $p=0.106$, $p = 0.106$, $p=0.106$. While this correlation is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level, it suggests a slight tendency for larger firms to have lower leverage, which could reflect their ability to finance operations through equity or other non-debt means. Larger firms may also have better access to capital markets, reducing the need for debt. Firm Size (FS), positive correlation with Tobin's Q: $r=0.455$, $r = 0.455$, $p<0.000$, $p < 0.000$, $p<0.000$. Larger firms are strongly associated with better firm performance, as noted earlier. This finding reinforces the view that firm size plays a critical role in influencing firm outcomes, possibly through better market positioning, access to resources, and economies of scale. On Insights and Recommendations: CEO Tenure's Negative Effect on Performance: The strong negative correlation between CEO tenure and Tobin's Q suggests firms should critically assess how long CEOs remain in power. Longer-tenured CEOs may need governance structures to prevent complacency or entrenchment, such as regular performance.

Table 3. REM Regression results

TBQ	Basic model			Moderated model		
	Coef.	z	P>z	Coef.	z	P>z
CEOT	-.0268337	-4.84	0.000	-.2189286	-5.41	0.000
BI	.0336106	3.26	0.000	.0032893	4.88	0.000
AQ	.0301539	4.40	0.000	.0413751	5.53	0.000
FL	-.081933	-14.51	0.000	-.0082783	-15.69	0.000
FS	.2997645	4.14	0.000	.2939315	4.14	0.000
_cons	2.870373	4.44	0.000	2.979792	4.67	0.000
BICEOT	-	-	-	.041018	-3.69	0.000
VIF	1.04			1.04		
Hetest	0.0061			0.0067		
Panel effects	0.0000			0.0000		
Hausman	0.5152			0.1367		
Model fitness	0.0000			0.0000		
R ²	0.4443			0.4473		
Obs	1,530			1,530		

Source: STATA 18, Version 4

Table 3 displays results from a Random Effects Model (REM) regression analyzing Tobin's Q (TBQ) with a basic and a moderated model, offering useful insights into the impact of CEO tenure (CEOT), board independence (BI), audit quality (AQ), firm leverage (FL), and firm size (FS) on firm performance (measured

by TBQ). Below is a detailed breakdown and insights into the statistical outcomes. CEO Tenure (CEOT): Basic Model: Coefficient = -0.0268, $z = -4.84$, $p < 0.000$. CEO tenure has a negative and statistically significant impact on Tobin's Q, suggesting that as the CEO's tenure increases, the firm's performance, as measured by Tobin's Q, tends to decline. Moderated Model: Coefficient = -0.2189, $z = -5.41$, $p < 0.000$. After introducing the moderation, the negative effect of CEO tenure on Tobin's Q becomes stronger. The more extended the CEO's tenure, the more likely it is that firm value decreases.

Board Independence (BI): Basic Model: Coefficient = 0.0336, $z = 3.26$, $p < 0.000$. Board independence positively affects Tobin's Q, implying that as the level of independence within the board increases, firm performance also improves. Moderated Model: Coefficient = 0.0033, $z = 4.88$, $p < 0.000$. The effect of board independence remains positive but weakens after interaction, suggesting that independence alone may not be the primary driver of performance. Audit Quality (AQ): Basic Model: Coefficient = 0.0302, $z = 4.40$, $p < 0.000$. Audit quality positively affects Tobin's Q. Higher-quality audits are associated with improved firm performance. Moderated Model: Coefficient = 0.0414, $z = 5.53$, $p < 0.000$. Audit quality's effect becomes even more pronounced when moderation is applied, indicating that better audits contribute significantly to firm value.

Firm Leverage (FL): Basic Model: Coefficient = -0.0819, $z = -14.51$, $p < 0.000$. Firm leverage has a significant negative impact on Tobin's Q, suggesting that higher debt levels are detrimental to firm performance. Moderated Model: Coefficient = -0.0083, $z = -15.69$, $p < 0.000$. After moderation, the negative impact of leverage remains strong and significant, reinforcing the detrimental effects of high leverage on firm value. Firm Size (FS): Basic Model: Coefficient = 0.2998, $z = 4.14$, $p < 0.000$. Firm size positively correlates with Tobin's Q, indicating that larger firms perform better financially. Moderated Model: Coefficient = 0.2939, $z = 4.14$, $p < 0.000$. The positive effect of firm size remains stable and significant in both models, highlighting its consistent role in firm performance. Interaction Term (BICEOT): Coefficient = 0.0410, $z = -3.69$, $p < 0.000$. The interaction between board independence and CEO tenure has a negative and significant impact on Tobin's Q. This suggests that the joint effect of a longer CEO tenure and board independence may hurt firm value, possibly indicating that excessively long-tenured CEOs reduce the effectiveness of board independence.

On Model Diagnostics, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF): A VIF of 1.04 across both models indicates no multicollinearity issues, meaning the independent variables are not highly correlated. Heteroskedasticity Test (Hetttest): The p-values (0.0061 and 0.0067) suggest the presence of heteroskedasticity. Although the REM corrects for panel effects, this issue could require further robustness checks. Panel Effects: Significant panel effects ($p = 0.0000$) in both models imply that unobserved heterogeneity across firms is present and should be accounted for using the random effects model. Hausman Test: The Hausman test values ($p = 0.5152$ and 0.1367) indicate that the random effects model is more appropriate than the fixed effects model. R-Squared: The R-squared values are 0.4443 for the basic model and 0.4473 for the moderated model. These values suggest that around 44% of the variation in Tobin's Q is explained by the variables in the model.

On Insights and Recommendations, CEO Tenure's Negative Impact: Firms may need to reassess the length of time CEOs remain in their positions. Long tenures could lead to diminishing returns in terms of firm performance, possibly due to entrenchment or resistance to innovation. Board Independence is Beneficial but Limited: While board independence positively influences firm performance, its impact diminishes when interacting with long-tenured CEOs. This suggests a nuanced dynamic where independent boards may not fully mitigate the negative effects of entrenched leadership. Audit Quality and Firm Leverage: Audit quality is a critical driver of firm performance, while high leverage consistently harms firm value. These findings support continued investment in high-quality audits and careful management of debt levels. Firm Size and Performance: Larger firms are shown to perform better, indicating that economies of scale or market dominance may be at play. Smaller firms might need to explore strategies for growth to achieve better financial outcomes. Heteroskedasticity: Although the models suggest heteroskedasticity, conducting further diagnostics or employing robust standard errors is worthwhile to ensure reliable conclusions. In conclusion, this regression analysis highlights the intricate dynamics between corporate governance factors and firm performance. CEO tenure, board independence, and audit quality are all significant drivers, with important moderating effects at play. The firm should focus on strategic governance practices to optimize performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the REM regression results in Table 3, we conclude and recommend the following: **CEO Tenure:** Basic Model: CEO tenure negatively affects Tobin's Q (TBQ) with a significant coefficient of -0.0268, indicating that longer CEO tenures are associated with a decline in firm performance. Moderated Model: The negative impact becomes stronger with a coefficient of -0.2189, showing a more pronounced decrease in performance as CEO tenure increases, suggesting risks of entrenchment and reduced organizational innovation over time. **Board Independence:** Basic Model: Board independence (BI) has a positive impact on TBQ (0.0336), indicating that firms with more independent boards perform better, aligning with good governance practices. Moderated Model: The positive effect of BI weakens slightly (0.0033), signaling that its influence may diminish when interacting with other factors like CEO tenure, suggesting a limitation in its impact when leadership is deeply entrenched. **Audit Quality:** Basic Model: Audit quality (AQ) is positively associated with firm performance (0.0302), supporting the notion that high-quality audits improve transparency and financial outcomes. Moderated Model: The impact of AQ increases (0.0414), indicating that stronger audit mechanisms have an amplified positive effect, particularly when moderated by other variables. **Firm Leverage:** Basic Model: Firm leverage (FL) has a strong negative association with TBQ (-0.0819), implying that higher debt levels detract from firm performance. Moderated Model: The negative impact remains robust (-0.0083), further emphasizing the detrimental effect of excessive leverage on financial performance. **Firm Size:** Basic and Moderated Models: Firm size (FS) positively affects TBQ (0.2998 and 0.2939), indicating that larger firms tend to perform better, likely benefiting from economies of scale and market power. **Interaction Term:** The interaction between board independence and CEO tenure (BICEOT) yields a significant negative impact (-0.0410), suggesting that long-tenured CEOs may undermine the positive influence of an independent board, potentially reducing the effectiveness of governance structures.

On Policy Recommendations: **CEO Tenure Limits:** Firms should implement policies to limit CEO tenure to prevent entrenchment, which can negatively affect innovation and firm performance. Establishing leadership renewal programs or fixed-term contracts may help to balance leadership stability with the need for fresh strategic perspectives. **Strengthen Board Independence:** While board independence is generally beneficial, its impact diminishes with entrenched leadership. Firms should empower independent directors with stronger oversight mechanisms, especially when dealing with long-serving CEOs. Boards should consider succession planning and regular assessments of CEO performance to mitigate negative moderating effects. **Enhance Audit Quality Standards:** The positive correlation between audit quality and firm performance calls for stricter regulatory frameworks and internal audit practices. Firms should invest in high-quality audit services and adopt technologies (such as AI and machine learning) for enhanced transparency and fraud detection. **Debt Management Policies:** Given the negative effect of leverage on firm value, firms should pursue conservative debt management strategies. Policymakers could introduce guidelines for optimal leverage ratios, particularly for firms in sectors prone to high volatility, to safeguard against financial distress. **Encourage Growth Strategies for Smaller Firms:** Since firm size positively influences performance, policymakers and firms should create programs to support smaller firms' growth through mergers, acquisitions, or market expansion strategies. Additionally, smaller firms should focus on scaling efficiently to benefit from market dynamics enjoyed by larger firms.

On Practical Recommendations: **CEO Performance Monitoring:** Implement ongoing CEO performance evaluations and feedback mechanisms, particularly for long-serving CEOs, to ensure that leadership remains aligned with evolving market dynamics and innovation. **Training and Empowerment of Independent Directors:** Independent board members should undergo continuous governance and financial training to strengthen their capacity to challenge entrenched leadership. Independent directors should be encouraged to take a more active role in firm strategy and risk oversight. **Leverage Control:** Firms should set internal leverage ceilings based on industry benchmarks and economic conditions, incorporating debt stress tests to assess potential risks during economic downturns. **Audit Quality Review:** Conduct regular reviews of audit processes and engage in third-party assessments to ensure audit firms meet high-quality standards, reducing risks of financial misreporting. **Growth-Enhancing Investments:** Smaller firms should focus on strategic investments in technology, R&D, and market expansion to grow their market presence. Programs for efficient capital utilization and scaling can enhance performance. **On a final thought:** The random effects model regression highlights critical governance-related factors influencing firm performance, particularly the moderating effects of entrenched leadership.

Strategic policies around CEO tenure, board structure, audit quality, and leverage management can significantly boost firm performance and long-term sustainability.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The earlier draft of this paper was presented at the NDA Management 2023 Conference. We thank the participants for giving constructive comments on this paper. However, despite the several comments received on this paper, all errors remain with the authors.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do creditors care about ESG performance? *International Journal of Management, Economics, and Social Sciences*, 13(5), 320-346.
- Abbas, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial statement fraud likelihood. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics*, 19(2), 100365.
- Abdullahi, K., Musa, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Are CEOs hedge against share price fall? *Accounting and Business Research*, 53(5), 243-263.
- Abdullahi, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of corporate governance on corporate social responsibility disclosure. *Research in Management in Accounting*, 7(1), 221-252.
- Abubakar, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Which corporate owners are relevant in reducing earnings management? *Finance, Accounting, and Economic Insights*, 9(23), 16-75.
- Adams, R. B., & Ferreira, D. (2009). Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 94(2), 291–309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2008.10.007>
- Adebowale, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of shareholder activism, on firm value. *Organisations and Markets in Emerging Economies*, 15(1)(4), 209-250.
- Adeleye, M., Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The role of shareholders in controlling tax aggressiveness. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 62(3), 1140-1191.
- Adewinmisi, G. O., Ahmed, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Audit committee independence and audit quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(3), 16-26.
- Adeyemi, E., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of board financial expertise on earnings quality in Nigerian listed companies. *NDA Original Research Papers*, 2024-9(4), 1-30.
- Ahmed, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Unlocking the power of corporate governance and its impact on financial stability. *Governance and Management Review*, 9(1), 71-109.
- Ahmed, D., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Institutional and board ownership and corporate financial performance in Nigeria. *Advances in Business Research*, 14, 111-132.
- Ahmed, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). New insights on board structure and income smoothing hypothesis. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 4(1), 784-803.
- Aivazian, V. A., Ge, Y., & Qiu, J. (2005). The impact of leverage on firm investment: Canadian evidence. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 11(1-2), 277–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2003.09.008>
- Alih, D. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Board characteristics and cost of capital of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance, Business and Management Studies*, 4(2), 80-94.
- Alzoubi, E. S. S. (2018). Audit quality and earnings management: Evidence from Jordan. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 30, 69–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intaccudtax.2017.12.001>
- Andrew, L., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Estimating a predictive model for share price based on the influence of the board attributes in Nigeria. *Global Finance, Accounting, and Economics Perspectives*, 9(18), 590-620.
- Anthonio, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). A corporate governance perspective on the audit committee and its role in improving earnings quality. *Advanced Research in Economics and Business Strategy*, 5(1), 78-107.
- Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Ownership structure, board of directors and financial performance: Evidence in Nigeria. *Global Review of Accounting and Finance*, 13(1), 77-98.
- Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve financial performance? Empirical evidence from Africa listed consumer retailing companies. *Management Studies*, 12(1), 111-124.
- Apochi, J. G., Yahaya, O. A., & Yusuf, M. J. (2024). The relationship between board diversity and CEO

turnover. *Brazilian Business Review*, 3(2), 1-45.

Arah, A. B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of SDGs on the socio-economic lives of people of Niger State. *Michigan Journal of Sustainability*, 12(1), 142-178.

Audu, R. A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Audit committee attributes and financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Management Sciences*, 3(3), 238-257.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Can the CEO reverse the increasing leverage of listed firms in Nigeria? *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 12(1), 423-433.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Determinants of environmental disclosure quality using Probit estimation among deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Warfare, Command and Capacity Building in Nigeria*. Archers.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Tenure and nationality among board members and audit quality in Nigerian Listed Firms. *Audit and Accounting Review*, 3(1), 40-57.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The role of women in sustainability reporting. *Wayamba Journal of Management*, 14(1), 16-34.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Building a corporate governance index for an emerging market ESG performance. *University of Auckland Business Review*, 27(2), 81-117.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). How women directors influence dividend policies? *Journal of Competition Law and Economics*, 20(2), 682-703.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of risk committee on sustainability disclosure. *Kardan Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 7(2), 137-172.

Awen, B. I., Adewinmisi, G. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). The influence of ownership structure on dividend policy in reducing agency problems in Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *Int Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(3), 99-111.

Awen, B. I., Lamido, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board size, independence and dividend policy in Nigeria. *Intl Journal of Economics and Finance*, 15(5), 72-91.

Awen, B. I., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the board of directors increase firm value? Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Korean Accounting Review*, 47(12), 82-97.

Awolola, J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do audit firms and audit committees enhance earnings quality? *Journal of Financial Economics and Accounting*, 9(13), 784-821.

Awolola, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of environmental, social, and governance reporting on investment decisions. *Business, Management, and Economics Engineering*, 22(1), 66-106.

Baba, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The powers of audit and risk committees in constraining earnings management. *Accounting Education*, 32(4), 1-17.

Bappa, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An analysis of the relationship between auditor independence and audit quality. *Universal Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(1), 32-55.

Bashir, I. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The effect of working capital management on the profitability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Management*, 46, 246-259.

Bhagat, S., & Bolton, B. (2008). Corporate governance and firm performance. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 14(3), 257–273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2008.03.006>

Black, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Which ownership structure is significant in ESG performance? *American Business Review*, 27(2), 635-664.

Busayo, E., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do women enhance intellectual capital? *The Journal of Finance*, 74(4), 2902-2934.

Charles, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The value relevance of intellectual capital. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 25(2), 233-254.

Chuma, N., Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of tenure diversity on earnings management. *Asian American Research Journal*, 4(2024), 1-30.

Dania, I. S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). CEO power and intangible assets. *Asian Academy of Management Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 18(2), 270-286.

DeFond, M. L., & Zhang, J. (2014). A review of archival auditing research. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 58(2-3), 275–326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2014.09.002>

Ebiprewei, G., Yahaya, O. A., & Chukwueze, C. (2024). The asymmetric effects of integrated reports on firm value. *Journal of Governance and Integrity*, 7(1), 748-772.

Faccio, M., Marchica, M. T., & Mura, R. (2016). CEO tenure, corporate risk-taking, and the efficiency of capital allocation. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 39, 193–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2016.02.008>

Francis, J. R., & Yu, M. D. (2009). Big 4 office size and audit quality. *The Accounting Review*, 84(5), 1521–1552. <https://doi.org/10.2308/accr.2009.84.5.1521>

Garba, M., Yahaya, O. A., & Ahmed, M. N. (2023). Firms characteristics and tax avoidance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria moderated by board tenure. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 13(1), 1-20.

Gimbason, J. T., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Ownership structure and sustainability reporting. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 12(1), 77-102.

- Gummi, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). How does the heterogeneity of institutional investors affect audit quality? *Journal of Alternative Finance*, 1(2), 211-233.
- Hadi, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and accounting information asymmetry. *Asian Journal of Management Studies*, 3(3), 42-56.
- Hall, M., & Weiss, L. (1967). Firm size and profitability. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 49(3), 319–331. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1926642>
- Haruna, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Foreign ownership and firm performance in the NGX 153 companies. *Korean Journal of Financial Studies*, 53(3), 392-437.
- Hassan, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An examination of the relationship between governance practices and financial reporting transparency. *International Journal of Management Technology and Engineering*, 14(5), 64-85.
- Ibrahim, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board demographic characteristics and cost of capital decisions. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting*, 5(2), 126-143.
- Ibrahim, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Ownership structure and leverage. *The Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 17(4), 239-258.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Which nomination committee attributes matter in improving financial performance? *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*, 7(9), 231-257.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An inquiry into the nexus between a CEO and working capital management quality. *J of Smart Economic Growth*, 9(1), 135-163.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Applying GMM technique to auditor and value relationship. *Economic and Business*, 37, 247-274.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Board of directors and financial statements fraud. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 12(1), 137-167.
- Itopa, E., Alexander, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board of directors and earnings management: Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 22(3), 45-59.
- Itopa, E., Imam, M., Musa, U., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Corporate governance and capital structure: Evidence from Nigeria listed financial services firms. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research* (2602-3385), 3(12), 75-89.
- Kabir, Y. I., Tnushi, P. S., Jada, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Ownership demographics and financial performance of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria moderated by firm size. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 13(3), 141-162.
- Khan, W. A., & Vieito, J. P. (2013). CEO tenure and firm performance. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 67, 55–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconbus.2013.01.003>
- Kim, Y. J., & Lee, S. M. (2020). CEO tenure, board independence, and firm performance: Evidence from South Korea. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 28(4), 421–439. <https://doi.org/10.1111/corg.2020.004>
- Lamidi, S., Yahaya, O. A., & Abdulwahab, A. I. (2024). Does board diversity influence a company's commitment to corporate social responsibility and sustainability initiatives? *Scientific Annals of Economics and Business*, 71(2), 315-349.
- Lamido, I. A., Ibrahim, M. F., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Review of Applied Management and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 581-590.
- Lamido, I. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A meta-analysis of female directors and instability in firm value in Nigeria. *China Journal of Accounting Studies*, 11(7), 325-337.
- Lawal, C., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Could board financial expertise enhance audit quality? *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 23(2), 89-125.
- Lawal, D., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The role of firm complexity in the nexus between board size and financial performance. *European Management Journal*, 42, 288-298.
- Lawal, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of corporate governance on integrated reporting. *Management Decision*, 62(1), 370-392.
- Lawal, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). What drives the Nigerian leverage? *Annals of Economics and Finance*, 25(1), 345-385.
- Liu, Y., Miletkov, M. K., Wei, Z., & Yang, T. (2015). Board independence and firm performance in China. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 30, 223–244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2014.12.004>
- Majumdar, S. K. (1997). The impact of size and age on firm-level performance: Some evidence from India. *Review of Industrial Organization*, 12(2), 231–241. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1007766324749>
- Mironenkova, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of ownership type on firm performance in an emerging market. *Journal of Applied Economic Research*, 23(1), 250-294.

- Mohammed, S. S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The intersection between ESG disclosure and audit committees. *Jurnal Pengurusan*, 70, 1-32.
- Muhammad, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The value relevance of ESG performance disclosure. *Journal of Sustainability Science and Management*, 19(4), 123-140.
- Murtala, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The effects of risk committee characteristics on bank asset quality. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Mgt and Technology*, 4(1), 35-51.
- Musa, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and firm value. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute Journal (Humanities and Social Sciences)*, 6(4), 204-220.
- Nasiru, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). How effective is the risk committee in reducing corporate operating risk in Nigeria? *Journal of Management and Research*, 11(1), 26-54.
- Okodo, B. D., Aliu, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Assessing the reliability of the internal audit functions: The issues. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, Economics and Finance*, 1(1), 46-55.
- Omotola, K., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The moderating effect of institutional ownership on board attributes and tax aggressiveness. *NDA Technical Papers*, 2024-9(5), 1-40.
- Onyabe, J. M., Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO and integrated reporting: Evidence from Africa listed communication services companies. *Afro-Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 13(2), 86-99.
- Peni, E., & Vähämaa, S. (2010). Female executives and earnings management. *Managerial Finance*, 36(7), 629-645. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03074351011050343>
- Petroski, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). On the independence of the board and its committees, and earnings quality. *South East European University Review*, 19(1), 39-78.
- Rahman, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Does it pay to be green? *Applied Economics*, 56(45), 5442-5469.
- Rajan, R. G., & Zingales, L. (1995). What do we know about capital structure? Some evidence from international data. *The Journal of Finance*, 50(5), 1421-1460. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1995.tb05184.x>
- Rojas, G. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Women on boards and corporate social responsibility disclosure. *Revista de Métodos Cuantitativos para la Economía y la Empresa (Journal of Quantitative Methods for Economics and Business Administration)*, 37, 29-69.
- Salihu, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Family ownership with asymmetric sustainability disclosure. *Business Research Quarterly*, 27(3), 346-375.
- Salisu, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of female CEO on company leverage. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 34, 81-107.
- Samaila, N., Suleiman, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate boards and leverage decisions. *Accounting Forum*, 47(2), 307-326
- Samuel, F., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Modelling and predicting corporate governance determinants of capital structure. *Dynamic Management Journal*, 8(2), 496-522.
- Shittu, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The effect of institutional ownership on sustainability disclosure in emerging markets, Nigeria in perspective. *The Financial Economist: Accounting, Auditing, and Finance*, 9(19), 74-109.
- Shokomi, L., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Sustainability committee and firm value. *NDA Open Access Articles*, 2024-9(3), 1-38.
- Shuaibu, K., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and dividend policy. *Economics and Business Quarterly*, 6(3), 125-141.
- Smith, L. A., Jones, K. P., & Taylor, M. J. (2017). The moderating role of board independence on the relationship between CEO tenure and firm performance in the U.S. *Journal of Corporate Governance*, 24(3), 45-61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2017.04.005>
- Sulaiman, L., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and auditor choice. *South Asian Journal of Finance*, 3(1), 38-59.
- Suleiman, T., Ladan, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do the sustainability committees matter in corporate financial performance? *Journal of Applied Economics and Business Studies*, 8(2), 23-64.
- Suleiman, U., Popoola, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Equity financing and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Innovation and Social Science*, 6(12), 618-624.
- Sumaila, D., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Could women directors reduce high leverage? *Journal of Sustainable Business and Economics and Finance*, 3(2), 17-42.
- Tighil, M., Yahaya, O. A., Tauhid, S., & Abdulfatah, L. A. (2024). The effects of board characteristics on the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 17(1), 314-324.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve energy information disclosure among Nigeria listed manufacturing firms? *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*, 26(3), 15-26.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of corporate ownership demographics and sustainability reporting quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 15(3), 393-410.

- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The impact of CEO female tenure diversity and nationality on Internal Control System Disclosure: Empirical Evidence from Nigeria. *Int Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences*, 10(2), 50-61.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). CEO characteristics and corporate risk taking. *International Journal of Corporate Governance*, 14(1), 94-116.
- Titman, S., & Wessels, R. (1988). The determinants of capital structure choice. *The Journal of Finance*, 43(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1988.tb02585.x>
- Tomasz, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The monitoring role of the CEO in enhancing audit quality. *Journal of Management and Financial Sciences*, 17(50), 120-150.
- Umar, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and bankruptcy risk using GMM approach. *Applied Finance and Accounting*, 9(1), 242-256.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board Committees' Independence and Intellectual Capital Efficiency in Corporate Nigeria. *The Journal of Bus.*, 8(1), 36-47.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Do corporate governance mechanisms improve earnings? *China Journal of Accounting Research*, 16, 1-13.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The dynamics between a CEO and risk disclosure in Nigeria. *Accounting and Auditing Review*, 30(1), 1-13.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Using binary regression analysis model to diagnose the effect of female directors on audit quality. *Reviews of Management Sciences*, 6(1), 70-89.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and credit ratings in Nigeria. *Int Journal of Economics, Management and Finance*, 2(1), 62-71.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Effect of board characteristics on firm value in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 47(1), 44-60.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The CEO power and sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria. *J. of Business Mgt. and Accounting*, 13(7), 106-125.
- Wang, Z., & Li, J. (2019). Board independence as a moderator of CEO tenure and firm performance in Chinese firms. *Asian Journal of Corporate Governance*, 15(1), 89–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajcg.2019.05.009>
- Yahaya, O. A. (2006). Empirical evidence on the effect of size on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Studies*, 11(4), 33-39.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2014). Social disclosure and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria listed firms. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting Research*, 10(2), 47-66.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2017). Firm performance and dividend policy: A panel data analysis of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Technology and Development*, 8(1), 306-322.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2018). Environmental reporting practices and financial performance of listed environmentally-sensitive firms in Nigeria. *Savanna: A Journal of the Environmental and Social Sciences*, 24(2), 403-412.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Intellectual capital management and financial competitiveness of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *Enugu State University of Technology Journal of Management Sciences*, 12(1&2), 86-96.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2021). Analysts' forecasts and stock prices: Evidence from Nigeria. *Iranian Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 5(2), 01-10.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the CEO improve intellectual capital? *International Journal of Finance, Accounting and Economics Studies*, 3(1), 84-100.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Chief executive officer and firm value: Evidence from Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *J of Econ & Financial Studies*, 10(3), 12-21.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Corporate governance and profitability: An Application of Agency Theory. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 34(2), 406-421.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does Board Tenure Diversity Influence Dividend Pay-Out? Evidence from Nigeria Non-Financial Services Sector. *International J. of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 7(2), 25-33.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEO characteristics affect dividend policy? *Review of Accounting Studies*, 27(2), 375-389.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEOs influence earnings management? *South African Journal of Accounting Research*, 36(2), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Electronic payments system and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Economics*, 5(20), 45-54.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Female directors and financial performance. Does audit committee play a role? *Advances in Accounting*, 58(C), 248-258.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Abdulfatah, L. A. (2022). Can auditors reduce earnings management activities? *Review of Accounting and Finance* (ISSN: 1475-7702), 22(4), 429-442.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alexander, A. A. (2015). Business process management and financial performance: An

exploratory study of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Accounting Frontier*, 17(1), 43–75.

Yahaya, O. A., & Alkasim A. (2021). Sustainability and profitability of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Accounting and Finance*, 6(1), 17-28.

Yahaya, O. A., & Andow, H. A. (2015). Capital structure and firm's financial performance: Panel evidence of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *Kaduna Business Management Review*, 2(1), 1-25.

Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. (2021). Board of directors and corporate social responsibility reporting of quoted companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 7(2), 38-52.

Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. G. (2022). The board of directors' influence on the intellectual capital of Nigeria listed firms. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 37(2), 1-17.

Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2020). Bank-specific attributes and operational efficiency: Evidence from Efficient-Structure Hypothesis. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 1087-1098.

Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2021). Chief executive officers and bankruptcy of quoted resources companies in Nigeria. *Fountain Journal of Mgt Sciences*, 10(2), 970-980.

Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2022). Does ownership structure lead to optimal financial structure? *Seisense Journal of Management*, 5(4), 51-64.

Yahaya, O. A., & Lamidi, Y. S. (2015). Empirical examination of the financial performance of Islamic bank in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 2(7), 1-13.

Yahaya, O. A., & Lamido, I. A. (2022). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance Review*, 10(1), 107-120.

Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Does board of directors improve profitability? *Accounting*, 8, 269-275.

Yahaya, O. A., & Ogwiji, J. (2021). Risk committee traits and profitability of Nigerian banking sector. *Accounting, Finance & Management: Texts and Applications*, 01-14.

Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2020). Firm life cycle and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 723-732.

Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Audit committee and integrated reporting. *European Research Studies Journal*, 25(4), 305-318.

Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Do audit fees and auditor independence affect audit quality? *Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 14(1), 66-80.

Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). The nexus between audit committee and audit fees. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 53(6), 966-984.

Yahaya, O. A., & Tijani, B. (2020). Internal corporate governance and intellectual capital of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *European J. of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 8(9), 98-112.

Yahaya, O. A., & Tijjani, B. (2021). Size, age and leverage of Nigeria quoted oil and gas corporations. *Advanced International Journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance*, 3(6), 51-60.

Yahaya, O. A., & Yakubu, I. (2022). Risk committee's influence on enterprise risk management. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(4): 120, 1-15.

Yahaya, O. A., & Yusuf, M. J. (2020). Ethical behavioural disclosure and financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. *Sustainable Business and Society in Emerging Economies*, 2(2), 13-20.

Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2014). Country-specific characteristics as determinants of financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting*, 3(2), 77-101.

Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). International financial reporting standards and earnings management behavior of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business Management*, 7(18), 70-82.

Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., Solanke, A. A., Onyabe, J. M. & Usman, S. O. (2015). Current assets management and financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Int Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 13, 45-56.

Yahaya, O. A., Lamidi, Y. S., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). The correlation between risk management and organizational performance: an empirical investigation using panel data. *Res J. of Finance and Accounting*, 6(16), 136-146.

Yahaya, O. A., Mohammed, I., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Board governance and sustainability disclosure of Nigeria Listed Deposit Money Banks. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 126-146.

Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). Determinants of productivity of listed deposit money banks: An empirical estimation using panel data. *Journal of Accounting*, 4(1), 79-93.

Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). International financial reporting standards and value relevance of accounting information of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Dev.*, 6(12), 85-93.

Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., Yusuf, M. J., & Bilyaminu, T. (2019). Financial mix and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 226-237.

Yahaya, O. A., Tanko, M., & Muhammad, L. M. (2017). Effects of corporate characteristics on earnings quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Management Sciences*, 8(1), 47-64.

- Yahaya, O. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Dania, I. S. (2015). International financial reporting standards' adoption and financial statement effects: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Research J. of Finance and Accounting*, 6(12), 107-122.
- Yakubu, J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do board meetings and remuneration influence environmental disclosure? *Asian Review of Financial Research*, 37(2), 150-191.
- Yakubu, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and variability in integrated reporting gravity. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 8(50), 234-255.
- Yang, C. H., & Chen, K. H. (2009). Are small firms less efficient? Empirical evidence from U.S. firms. *Small Business Economics*, 32(4), 375–395. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-007-9082-x>
- Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO attributes and financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 11(2), 112-124.
- Zubairu, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of audit quality on financial reporting quality, mediated by audit committee effectiveness in Nigerian listed companies. *European Management Review*, 21(1), 1-22.
- Zumbiali, V., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do foreign and institutional ownerships enhance the quality of financial reports? NDA Working Paper Series Number 2024-8/26, 1-33.